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**COMMUNICATION AS A SOCIAL PRACTICE: EXPLORING THE MEANING OF
SMOKING AMONG FARMWORKERS IN SITIO LALAWAN,
MALAYBALAY CITY, BUKIDNON**

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2022

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REYMARK P. MALINDA

26 July 2022

Acceptance Page

This thesis titled “Communication as a Social Practice: Exploring the Meaning of Smoking among Farmworkers in Sitio Lalawan, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree Master of Development Communication (MDC).

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Biographical Sketch

Reymark P. Malinda earned his bachelor's degree in Development Communication from Bukidnon State University in 2014. He considers himself a lifelong learner. Hence, apart from experiential learning, he widens his knowledge through further studies. In 2017, he obtained his Certificate of Teaching from the University of Science and Technology of Southern Philippines – Cagayan de Oro (USTP-CDO). He successfully passed the Licensure Examination for Teachers in the same year. In 2018, he completed a course titled Contact Center Services NCII at the Philippine Call Center Institute.

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Acknowledgement Page

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ABSTRACT

MALINDA, REYMARK PADLA. University of the Philippines Open University. July 2022. Communication as a Social Practice: Exploring the Meaning of Smoking among Farmworkers in Sitio Lalawan, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon.

Adviser: Benjamina Paula Gonzalez-Flor, PhD

Smoking is a major health risk that affects both smokers and non-smokers. Although extensive studies on smoking, mostly quantitative, have been carried out worldwide, little is known about the smoking phenomenon in the Philippines, especially in rural areas, wherein smoking is highly prevalent. Through the sociocultural lens, this qualitative study was undertaken using the narrative approach to identify the meaning of smoking among the farmworkers of Sitio Lalawan, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon. Individual open interview among seven participants was used as the means for data collection. The interview transcripts were then analyzed through restorying and narrative thematic analysis, which yielded five themes, representing their meanings of smoking. For the farmworkers, smoking was a parent and peer's influence, a means to manage negative feelings and emotions, a thought provoker and organizer, a culture among friends, and an integral part of life. These findings demonstrated that family and peer smoking resulted in behavior modeling. Smoking was a coping mechanism when they experienced all types of life problems that caused stress. Smoking aided them at work by improving their mental capacities, thereby boosting productivity and efficiency. Socializing with smoker friends formed a culture, wherein they observed social norms, namely smoking while conversing, sharing cigarettes, and looking for ways to obtain cigarettes or find their alternatives. Ultimately, smoking was an inseparable component of their lives; it is attributed to the previously mentioned meanings alongside nicotine dependence, perceived ill outcomes of smoking cessation, and the absence of perceptible evidence, displayed by family members who smoked, that smoking damages the health. In conclusion, smoking is their life and breaking it would seriously result in unweaving the social fabric that binds the members of the farming community. Public health experts, concerned agencies, development communication practitioners, and the local government unit of Malaybalay are enjoined to consider these findings in crafting or improving smoking cessation programs and campaigns and strengthening current smoking policies intended for the farmworkers.

Keywords: Farmworkers, Meaning-making, Narrative Inquiry, Smoking

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Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

Good health is a significant part of people's lives which everyone hopes to maintain throughout existence. However, an unhealthy lifestyle has become a major stumbling block towards achieving this. At the forefront is cigarette or tobacco smoking, hereafter referred to as smoking – a preventable cause of morbidity and premature mortality worldwide (Forouzanfar *et al.*, 2015; Gometz, 2011). Smoking is a major risk factor directly linked to developing lung, breast, and prostate cancer (Lariscy, 2019; Saha *et al.*, 2007). Smoking is likewise a substantial risk factor for important bacterial and viral infection, particularly tuberculosis (TB) (Arcavi & Benowitz, 2004). In the recent 2020 global TB report by Chakaya *et al.* (2021), two thirds of the global total of people with TB (10 million) is constituted by eight developing countries, namely India (26%), Indonesia (8.5%), China (8.4%), the Philippines (6.0%), Pakistan (5.7%), Nigeria (4.4%), Bangladesh (3.6%), and South Africa (3.6%). It was particularly emphasized in the report that smoking is one of the key drivers of TB along with undernutrition, poverty, diabetes, and household air pollution.

Moreover, smoking causes deleterious human effects particularly cardiovascular diseases. Heart attacks have been associated with cigarette smoking (Parkin *et al.*, 2001). Globally, smoking-related diseases tallied 6.4 million mortality: 52.2% of this was recorded in China, India, the United States (US), and Russia (Reitsma *et al.*, 2017). The annual smoking-related deaths recorded in the US are 420,284 (Lariscy, 2019). Notably, tobacco epidemic has been largely concentrated on low- and middle-income countries having 8 million deaths each year (Lancet, 2012).

Of this number, 7 million are direct smokers and the remaining 1 million is related to second-hand smoke (SHS) (World Health Organization [WHO], 2020).

Owing to the overwhelming number of mortality rates and health complications caused by smoking, improving people's health is one of the major concerns of the United Nations, listed third in its Sustainable Development Goals (SDG): Good Health and Well-being. The WHO also responded to this call. It crafted effective tobacco control policies through the Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (FCTC) (WHO, 2005) – the first global treaty, contained in the MPOWER Policy Package (WHO, 2008). FCTC is aimed at reaffirming the right of all individuals to the highest health standard.

In the Philippines, smoking remains a health risk, as evidenced by the 2020 global TB report. The country's tobacco industry was described as “the strongest tobacco lobby in Asia” (Alechnowicz & Chapman, 2004, p. 71). As a response, the country has adopted FCTC in 2005. Several control programs and policies have also been implemented in the country since then. The Joint Memorandum Circular No. 2010-01 titled “Protection of the Bureaucracy against Tobacco Industry Interference” in 2010 mandates the government agencies to avoid contact with the tobacco industry and to be transparent and accountable when there are necessary dealings with it (Civil Service Commission, 2010). Sin Tax Law (Republic Act No. 10351), enacted into law in 2013, restructures the excise tax on alcohol and tobacco products. Lastly, the most recent one is the Graphic Health Warnings (GHW) Law (Republic Act No. 10643), which was ratified in 2014 and implemented after eight months since the law took effect. The said law requires picture-based warnings on cigarette packs, occupying 50% of the front and back panels.

The Philippine government's effort has yielded positive outcomes as demonstrated in the 2015 Global Adult Tobacco Survey (GATS) result, which was jointly carried out by the Department of Health (DOH), Philippine Statistics Authority, WHO, and Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. In the survey, it was recorded that there was a 19.9% decline from 29.7% in 2009 to 23.8% in 2015 of adults, who reported current tobacco use in any form with 2015's prevalence rate of 22.1% and 25.3% in urban areas and rural areas, respectively (DOH, 2015). It was also disclosed that on one hand, around 15.9 million Filipinos are tobacco users with a daily average consumption of 11 cigarettes. It was reported as well that in the past month from the day the survey was conducted, 3.6 million adults were exposed to SHS in the workplace and 24 million at home. It was further revealed that 95% of adults believed that smoking causes serious illnesses but only 44.6% thought of quitting smoking.

It was also divulged in the survey that Filipinos, despite being in a low-income country, still spend an average monthly cigarette expenditure of Php 678.4, which could have been used for other more important household needs. Notwithstanding the gradual decrease of smoking rates from 2009 to 2015, there remain millions of Filipinos who continue to smoke and are affected by SHS. SHS plagues a large proportion of adults despite the passing of national law and a few local government ordinances (Baquilod *et al.*, 2013). Hence, smoking is still a major health threat that impoverishes Filipinos even more.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

With the information laid out in the preceding section, smoking indeed causes serious long-term health problems, which have been claiming millions of lives worldwide. A lot of Filipinos are engaged in the smoking activity and have also been affected by its detrimental effects. In a recent cross-sectional study of Yamaguchi *et al.* (2021) on lifestyle behaviors – including smoking – associated with the progression and prevalence of non-communicable diseases (NCDs) among 160 Filipino adults in Muntinlupa City, it was found out that along with salt intake, duration of tobacco use is positively associated with hypertension. The study also revealed that men tend to smoke than women, which supports the findings of Yen & Tan (2021), who highlighted that Filipino men's propensity for smoking is high. In a similar vein, Reitsma *et al.* (2017) demonstrated that there is no significant decrease in daily smoking prevalence among Filipino males since 1990. Highest current smoking rate was found among male rural dwellers as underlined by Punzalan *et al.* (2013). Yamaguchi *et al.* (2021) further discovered that smoking control is significantly related to income level – that is, those with daily incomes ranging from Php 300 and below have high incidence of smoking.

Consistent with the case in Muntinlupa City and what was disclosed by Punzalan *et al.* (2013), vulnerable people from the marginalized sectors are not spared. Smoking prevalence is highly observed among male farmworkers in a rural area in Southern Philippines, specifically in Purok-4, Sitio Lalawan, Barangay Linabo, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon. Although a part of Bukidnon's capital city, Sitio Lalawan is not urbanized. Farming and farm labor are the people's main sources of living. Surprisingly, this health epidemic exists despite the presence of conspicuous graphic

health warning signs on cigarette packs and the implementation of the Malaybalay City Ordinance No. 884 Series of 2017 that prohibits the “use, sale distribution, and advertisement of cigarettes and other tobacco products in certain places; and imposes penalties for violations.” With the ratification of the Sin Tax Law, the prices of cigarettes and other tobacco products have dramatically increased. This draws into question why farmworkers are willing to allocate some of their money for cigarettes and other vices even though they only earn less and could hardly make ends meet. Thus, there is a need to explore and understand how farmworkers in the said area regard smoking in their lives.

Additionally, research work related to the meaning of smoking in the Philippines, more so in marginalized sectors involving farmworkers, is relatively inexistent. Rather, most investigations are largely focused on adolescents, youth, students, and women in other countries. Also, existing knowledge on smoking in the country is obtained through quantitative approach (e.g., Yamaguchi *et al.*, 2021), which demands the conduct of further investigation using qualitative means. The present study took this as one of its points of departure.

Research Questions

In this work, the researcher studied and explored the experiences of the farmworkers in Sitio Lalawan, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, Philippines. The researcher was interested in the phenomena of conceptualizing smoking in the context of having a healthy lifestyle. The goal of the study is to take on a narrative approach in understanding the meaning of smoking among the farmworkers in the locality. It intended to answer the general question: *What does it mean for the farmworkers to smoke?*

The following are the main research questions:

1. How do the farmworkers define smoking?
2. How are the concepts of smoking communicated and articulated by the farmworkers through their stories?
3. How do the farmworkers' meanings of smoking define their actions?

Objectives of the study

In general, this research aimed to find out the meaning of smoking from the point of view of the farmworkers who experienced it.

Specifically, to answer the research questions, the study sought to:

1. Describe the farmworkers' meaning-making of smoking;
2. Explain the farmworkers' concepts of smoking with respect to their stories; and
3. Analyze how the farmworkers' meanings of smoking enforce them to smoke.

Significance of the Study

As meaning is purely subjective and can vary from one person to another, this study would add new insights into the meaning of smoking as perceived by new set of participants – farmworkers – whose age, educational, cultural, and socio-economic backgrounds, and experiences may be different from previous studies. Hence, the results of this study may present a new perspective on how smoking is communicated to this set of audience.

Smoking is considered a serious health threat, more so in this time of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic. Several studies have demonstrated that there is a strong association between smoking and COVID-19 severity, thereby

leading to or increasing the risk of death (Dessie & Zewotir, 2021; Grundy *et al.*, 2020; Haddad *et al.*, 2021; Harrison *et al.*, 2021; Mohsin *et al.*, 2021; Xie *et al.*, 2021). Correspondingly, smoking may also promote the spread of the virus through gathering and sharing of tobacco among smokers (Xie *et al.*, 2021). Ergo, conducting studies related to this matter is highly significant and relevant even up to the present time.

This work will be deemed useful, particularly in the local government of Malaybalay City and other government and private health sectors in healthcare policymaking. It will shed light on making informed decisions to public health practitioners and institutions as to which among the existing interventions relevant to smoking cessation is the most appropriate one to utilize or modify. This will also serve as a guide in developing another anti-smoking program or to augment the implementation of the City Ordinance in Malaybalay if needed. In general, this study will buttress the international organizations (e.g., United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal 3: Good Health and Well-being) and national government's initiatives in eliminating or at least decreasing the smoking prevalence in the country. The pervasiveness of smoking among farmworkers in the present study's setting only implies that existing health interventions like graphic health warnings on cigarette packs and banning of smoking in public spaces are inadequate. Thus, understanding why they smoke might help in developing comprehensive, tailor-made or customized community smoking prevention efforts.

Finally, this study used the qualitative method, which has not been extensively employed in the previous studies on smoking in the Philippines. It utilized the narrative approach to address its research objectives. The application of this approach in the study is described in the succeeding sections, particularly in the methodology.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The participants only included adult farmworkers who are current smokers – non-smokers were excluded since this study did not make a comparison between smokers and non-smokers. Adult was exactly chosen to establish distinct and population-based variations from the discussants in previous studies. Since this study was only conducted in Sitio Lalawan, the results will not represent all farmworkers in Barangay Linabo, other Barangays in Malaybalay, and the rest of rural farmworkers in the Philippines. In terms of the topic, the study only explored the meanings of smoking among the participants and the concepts they associate with it. Even if relevant, the health status and effects or perceived effectiveness of graphic health warning signs on cigarette packs were excluded since they require different parameters and instruments for data gathering. Additionally, they do not directly contribute to the objectives of the present study.

Chapter 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

As detailed in the previous section, smoking has been known to negatively affect a large number of people globally through first- and second-hand smoke. To determine further the current knowledge about the smoking phenomenon in the world and in the Philippines, thereby establishing the research gaps, it was necessary to first understand the basic information of smoking and tobacco, review early studies that identified the perceptions or views of smoker participants and respondents about smoking, explore the current status of smoking prevalence in the rural areas and seek the conception of smoking among the farmers, whose type of work are the same as that of the farmworkers. It was also relevant to explore the outcomes of the smoking cessation programs for us to gauge their effectivity by relating them to the current statistics and what is happening in reality, especially in the present work's research area. These are all elaborated in the following subsections.

Smoking and Tobacco

Smoking is the “act of inhaling and exhaling fumes of burning plant material” (Henningfield *et al.*, 2020, para. 1). The outset of cigarette smoking can be traced back to the 15th century when Columbus imported tobacco to Europe. Later on, this was abused. Today, it is considered an injurious stimulant (Zalewska *et al.*, 2009). One plant material commonly used in producing cigarettes is tobacco (*Nicotiana*). When burned, its smoke emits over 4,000 chemicals including nicotine that causes addiction (Benjamin, 2011). Nicotine addiction results in deleterious health consequences like

chronic diseases, particularly lung cancer that only manifests at older ages (Bonnie *et al.*, 2015). Other health conditions caused by this include heart and lung diseases, stroke, diabetes, and chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases (Centers for Disease and Control Prevention, 2020).

Perceived Meaning of Smoking

Owing to smoking's adverse health effects, this issue has been extensively investigated by scholars to develop smoking prevention and cessation programs. Some of their works include exploring people's ideas, meanings, and concepts associated with smoking.

Meaning of smoking among different sets of participants had been previously carried out mainly through qualitative means. Focus group discussions (FGDs) and in-depth interviews, and thematic analysis are commonly utilized method for data collection and data analysis, respectively. A handful of scholars also attempted to unravel the connotation of smoking through quantitative approach using survey for data gathering and only a few one that utilized mixed method. It is worthy to note that majority of the participants of the said studies were students, adolescents, young adults, and women who were all from foreign countries.

Almost all unveiled meanings are consistent with one another while others are relatively ambivalent, which are primarily influenced by a range of underlying factors – age, gender, culture, religion, and socioeconomic status among others. Out from the results of related studies involving different participants, four salient themes that constitute the meaning of smoking have emerged. First, smoking is a form of social practice that fosters socialization, thereby creating communities. Second, it is

regarded as a vehicle for group acceptance particularly among adolescents, youth and students. Third, it is used for emotional management. Lastly, smoking shapes image creation.

Smoking as a Social Practice and Lubricant for Socialization

Social practice refers to “everyday practices and the way these are typically and habitually performed in (much of) a society” (Holtz, 2014, p. 1). It is regarded as a meaningful part of people’s lives. Reckwitz (2004) cited that these practices are considered social “because they are similar for different individuals at different points of time and locations” (p. 250). This concept is commonly observed among youth, adolescent, and college students whose smoking habit is highly prevalent with a global prevalence of 8.9% (131 countries) among youth (Warren *et al.*, 2006) and 5.7% for college students (Awono & Sibetcheu, 2008). Hence, over the years, most of the investigations related to unpacking the meanings of smoking have been largely concentrated on them with great emphasis on curiosity as the major reason for smoking initiation (Anjum *et al.*, 2016).

Smoking is regarded by young people as socially acceptable (Watson *et al.*, 2003) and a social tool, developing broader social networks and groups (Subramaniam *et al.*, 2015; Tilleczek & Hine, 2006). Within this group, they perceive smoking as a social practice in which they simultaneously do the activity and share cigarettes that in turn foster bonding and social interaction with others in parties, disco bars, and cafés (Markham *et al.*, 2001; Sæbø *et al.*, 2017; Thrasher & Bentley, 2006). In these social settings, smoking builds a work-based community among young working adults, wherein it gives them a profitable time to reach out to their coworkers and managers in an informal approach especially for those with less advantaged

socioeconomic status. In a recent study conducted by Onen & Watson (2021), among individuals aged 25 to 35 years old, the participants disclosed that smoking enabled them to survive in social activities, thereby creating a strong bond among the members of the friend group. The participants further shared that smoking made conversation fluent and enjoyable, which shaped smoking as a lubricant for socialization as described by Miething *et al.* (2016).

For high school students in Turkey (Yuksel & Corbett, 2005) and Bangladeshi adolescents living in the United Kingdom (Markham *et al.*, 2001), smoking was not socially acceptable at their age because of some religious and cultural reasons. However, they still regarded tobacco as an emblem of social bonding, which enforced them to engage in the smoking activity. Personal meanings were also attached, highlighting that they did not want a person to smoke alone (Hsia & Spruijt-Metz, 2008; Spruijt-Metz *et al.*, 2004).

Meanwhile, consistent with the accounts of the previously mentioned discussants, smoking acts as an equalizer in a social environment and facilitates social relationships for women, giving them an opportunity to build a connection with others (Greaves, 2015; Humphreys *et al.*, 2011). The results of the study of Humphreys *et al.* (2011) revealed that smoking forged strong relationships instead of untying the bond among professional women. In the same study, one participant emphasized that she can socialize well with others through smoking and that it built connections among her friends, who were also smokers. The same case also applies to adult smokers aged 22-52 from the United Kingdom (Collins *et al.*, 2002). For them, smoking aided social interactions. One discussant shared that smoking lubricated the conversation with fellow smokers even they are strangers. In the same manner, out of 96 respondents

with mental disorders hospitalized in a psychiatric ward in Brazil, 18 of them reported that smoking has the ability to smoothen interaction, stating that the chat got better when picking up cigarettes (Oliveira *et al.*, 2015).

Smoking as a Vehicle for Group Acceptance

Smoking as a way for group acceptance is particularly observed among teens, adolescence, and college students. For some of them, the primary objective in the school context is to fit in or gain acceptance more than the academic goals (Eccles & Roeser, 2011). In the course of attaining this goal, one must take on peers' values and change their behavior based on the group's norms – smoking to name one (Amos & Bostock, 2007; Hsia & Spruijt-Metz, 2003; Johnston *et al.*, 2012; Scales *et al.*, 2009; Subramaniam *et al.*, 2015). Failure to do so and rejecting an offer to smoke are considered impolite and rude since they believe that smoking and offering a cigarette while celebrating with friends are regarded as proper, right, and polite behavior (Hsia & Spruijt-Metz, 2003).

In the study of Amos & Bostock (2007), the participants, who were Scottish smokers aged 15 to 16 years old, treated smoking as a vehicle to fit in and group acceptance and this was the major reason of their smoking behavior. In the same study, boys and girls inextricably linked smoking to drinking. They posited that smoking complemented well with drinking alcohol in bars. For boys, smoking and drinking were considered normal activities that were done in a group, while girls associated them with leisure activities. In these social settings, it cannot be avoided that there will be repeated offers of cigarettes for those who do not smoke, ridiculing them if they reject the offer, and nagging them about their reasons and among many others

(Subramaniam *et al.*, 2015). Hence, it is not surprising that peer or social pressure, acting as an influential determinant of experimentation and smoking, likewise permeates (Johnston *et al.*, 2012). This claim is supported by the systemic review and meta-analysis of Leshargie *et al.* (2019), wherein it was found out that peer pressure was a major predictor of smoking among this age group.

Smoking as a Tool for Emotion Management

Each individual has a unique approach in dealing with daily struggles that affect the emotional state. Across all ages in the extant literature, smoking has been associated with managing negative and fostering positive emotions. Negative emotions shared by participants and respondents in empirical studies included stress (Darlow & Lobel, 2012; Hsia & Spruijt-Metz, 2008; Onen & Watson, 2021; Watson *et al.*, 2003; Yuksel & Corbett, 2005), anxiety, depression (Eckerdt & Corradi-Webster, 2010), bad mood, boredom (Hsia & Spruijt-Metz, 2003; Humphreys *et al.*, 2011; Thrasher & Bentley, 2006; Yuksel & Corbett, 2005), anger, tension (Greaves, 2015), and sadness (Bronars *et al.*, 2018).

In the work of Darlow & Lobel (2012) about smoking among undergraduate students in a northeastern public university in the US, the concept of motivational flexibility was introduced, which suggests that behavior, such as smoking, becomes common when they have multiple reasons in engaging with such behavior; hence, a particular behavior varies across instances. Results disclosed that the day-to-day shifting of motives towards smoking among light smokers was highly associated with a greater frequency of smoking. Notably, one leading motivation for smoking was to release stress as self-reported by 29.6% of the study's total population. In another

study of Thrasher & Bentley (2006) on the meaning of smoking to 43 Mexican university students, it was panned that cigarette smoking and sharing offered them a momentary escape from their problems and relieve boredom, shoring up positive perception towards cigarettes. In the same vein, Greaves (2015) revealed that cigarette smoking suppressed anger, tension, and irritation among marginalized and self-described feminist women in Australia and Canada. One respondent accentuated that smoking helped her in controlling her emotions – not to bark at people when she was angry. Likewise, native pregnant women (smokers and non-smokers) in Alaska, the US opined that smoking managed negative affect like loneliness and sadness during pregnancy (Bronars *et al.*, 2018).

Several scholars have also underscored that across ages and genders, smoking is considered a pleasure giver, providing safety feeling and self-control (Antin *et al.*, 2018; Borderías *et al.*, 2015; Dias & Turato, 2006; Jenks, 1994; Nivethitha & Jain, 2018; Oliveira *et al.*, 2015; Rocha *et al.*, 2019). Held as a coping tool (Rugkåsa *et al.*, 2001; Scales *et al.*, 2009; Subramaniam *et al.*, 2015), smoking also gives happiness, enjoyment (Clark *et al.*, 2017; Yegenoglu *et al.*, 2006), and comfort (Aryal & Bhatta, 2015). This phenomenon can be explained by notion of culture of dependence, which is manifested in various ways. One of which is the mere addiction to cigarettes or nicotine, which brings pleasure to individuals (Henningfield *et al.*, 2020).

In the quantitative study of Borderías *et al.* (2015), involving 25,521 Spanish high school students aged 14 to 18 years old, the results revealed that the main reasons why they engaged themselves in smoking activity were joyfulness (58.6%) and relaxation (53.69%). This finding is also consistent with the result of the

quantitative investigation of Nivethitha & Jain (2018) wherein nearly half of the surveyed total population (43 out of 101), who were college students from Kanchipuram District, India, disclosed that they experienced a pleasurable feeling during their experimental smoking phase. Additionally, the perceived benefits of smoking among 315 young adults (college students) in Nepal were likewise examined by Aryal and Bhatta (2015). In the said study, data from the self-administered and semi-structured questionnaire unveiled that both smokers and non-smokers scored highest on the item asking them if they believe smoking would be relaxing.

Meanwhile in Brazil, the recent cross-sectional, population-based study of Rocha *et al.* (2019) involved 1,054 adults, aged 40 years or older, of which 183 were smokers. In the mentioned work, the University of São Paulo Reasons for Smoking Scale (USP-RSS) recorded that the prevalence of smoking among this population was relatively high (17.4%). On top of that, it was also tallied that the highest score in USP-RSS domain determinants was given to pleasures of smoking followed by tension reduction and physical dependence. It is also worth highlighting that low economic class and low education level were the major characteristics of smokers. Agreeing with these results is the study of Clark *et al.* (2017) whose part of their study's objectives was to determine the self-reported smoking reasons of 235 people living with psychotic illness. The reasons-for-smoking questionnaire unravelled that enjoyment and concentration were two of the key reasons for smoking next to weight control.

Smoking as a Driver for Image Creation

Smoking is essentially equated to projecting an image and identity. In the context of male adolescents, smoking is a symbol of masculinity, which is closely

linked to potency, wisdom, and bravery (Hsia & Spruijt-Metz, 2003; Ng *et al.*, 2007). According to Gana *et al.* (2018), smoking is an attitude that each “real man” should adopt. Smoking is also an emblem of passage to adulthood especially for boys (Gana *et al.*, 2018; Tilleczek & Hine, 2006; Yuksel & Corbett, 2005). Supporting this view is the result of the investigation of Ioannoua (2010) involving young Cypriots, who specifically linked smoking to the traits of a “macho” and “grown-up.”

Markham *et al.* (2001) and Watson *et al.* (2003) accentuated that smoking posed a cool image among adolescents. In the same manner, smoking was also viewed by teenage boys in Indonesia as a symbol of socioeconomic status (Ng *et al.*, 2007); the prices and brands of cigarettes were used to reflect the socioeconomic status of their peers. For them, puffing highly expensive cigarettes boosted self-confidence, making them more superior to their friends.

In the study of Hsia & Spruijt-Metz (2003), participated by Chinese American and Taiwanese American college students, particularly boys in their adolescent years, smoking was described as a form of rebellion, anger with teachers, and defiance to school authorities. It was considered a contrivance to show bravery since student smokers openly challenged the authority, making them “heroes” by their peers.

Contrarily, women held different views about smoking in terms of projecting an image. For them, the beginning of cigarette consumption included glamour, charm, and independence (Eckerdt & Corradi-Webster, 2010). Well-educated women smokers perceived smoking as an anti-establishment rebel since it is prohibited and banned in most bars (Humphreys *et al.*, 2011). In the work of Greaves (2015), smoking was regarded by women as risk-taking, rebellion, and independence, which were primarily influenced by advertising themes by the tobacco industry. A participant

pointed out that smoking was something that made her cool since projecting a cool image was part of her rebel side. Other young women have also a positive perceived health stance towards smoking particularly about having a good body figure; they regarded it as a driver for weight control (Allbutt *et al.*, 1995; Markham *et al.*, 2001).

Smoking in the Rural Areas

The prevalence of smoking in rural areas (25.3%) is high compared with the urban areas (22.1%). In the US, adults and adolescents in the countryside are more likely to be tobacco users (Pesko & Robarts, 2017). They are even less at par in terms of the decreasing smoking rates in the country (Buettner-Schmidt *et al.*, 2019). Hosseinpoor *et al.* (2011) cited that the high smoking rates in rural areas were attributed to demographic and social factors, namely lower income and education levels as well as higher unemployment rates. The work of Karamina *et al.* (2018) advanced that there was a significant relationship between employment and smoking habits with self-employed and employers of permanent employees were found to be heavy smokers. Agreeing to this point is the findings of Yang *et al.* (2016) who described that occupation, particularly being a farmer, was the key determinant of hardcore smoking in some rural areas in China. The same case is also true for three rural regions in France, wherein active smoking prevalence was observed among farmers (Roux *et al.*, 2017). Meanwhile, Sudarmin *et al.* (2019) discovered that smokers in Kodingareng Island, Indonesia viewed smoking behavior as not an issue when they make good money – a work culture that influenced them to smoke.

Smoking for Farmers

In the case of Chinese farmers and non-farmers, social factors, namely cigarette smoking, exchanging, and gifting were indispensable in their rural family life – these factors were primarily rooted in traditional familism and collectivism (Mao *et al.*, 2014). Mao *et al.* (2014) postulated that smoking was used in wider social interactions including simple family gatherings. Hence, this has been a major barrier to smoking cessation. These findings concur well with Swatan *et al.* (2020), whose study revealed that the high smoking rate in a rural area in Indonesia, where farming-related works are common, was deeply rooted in cultural orientation. The study indicated that cigarette was offered in social meetings and a sign of friendship; it was impolite when someone rejects the host's offer. Clearly, smoking is attributed to social control, predominantly maintaining a social relationship.

Smoking Cessation Efforts

As a response to this global health issue, a handful of effective smoking prevention and cessation programs have been implemented including peer education, theatre in health promotion, media advocacy, community mobilization, social marketing, motivational interviewing, mass media campaigns, and setting-based approach (Golechha, 2016). One major ubiquitous campaign is the graphic health warning sign on cigarette packs, which has been adopted by the Philippines' Department of Health (DOH) since 2015 through Republic Act No. 10643. A literature review paper found out that this effort is effective (Noar *et al.*, 2016). Another review paper about the perceived effectiveness of this anti-smoking program in Asian countries revealed that health warning signs are regarded as “effective in deterring

smoking initiation among non-smokers and stimulating smoking cessation among smokers” (Ratih & Susanna, 2018, p. 1). In the Philippines, the report of Braganza *et al.* (2016) also leans towards the same direction, underscoring that “graphic health warnings are effective in prompting smokers who buy on per-stick basis to think about the dangers of smoking, which in turn, is associated with increased intention to quit smoking” (para. 1). Despite these seemingly positive data, smoking prevalence remains high among farmworkers, the participants of the present study, in Sitio Lalawan. There could be several factors affecting this. Hence, qualitative investigation on the underlying meaning, reasons, and perceptions of smoking should be carried out.

Deficiencies or Gaps

Interestingly, out of the obtained reports and research works, there are only two related studies investigating the smoking meaning or perception that involved farmers and rural villagers. Notably, all of them were conducted outside of the Philippines. The first one – accomplished using qualitative method and anchored on Stokols’ Socio-Ecological Model – mainly focused on exploring personal and social determinants, playing a key role in smoking promotion among Chinese (Mao *et al.*, 2014). The second study, carried out through a quantitative method, revolved around analyzing the determinants of tobacco smoking addiction in Indonesian rural areas (Swatan *et al.*, 2020). Clearly, the objectives of both studies are contextually different from the present study – to explore the meaning of smoking guided on sociocultural tradition and social constructivism. In particular, the present study also used different qualitative approach (narrative) to attain its research objectives.

Moreover, the participants of the two mentioned studies were not entirely farmers or farmworkers – they only constituted a small fraction of the total number of participants. Also, the discussants of the previous studies on meaning of smoking were mostly children, adolescents, high school and university students, and women from other countries. Thus, the result of the previous studies and the present one may vary considering that this study specifically chose Filipino farmworkers as its participants. Additionally, researchers have not treated the meaning of smoking in much detail among Filipinos, particularly in the rural or less urbanized areas. No account has been documented yet about the same matter that involved the members of a different marginalized group (i.e., the farmworkers) in the Philippines.

Aside from representing the narratives of this population in the foregoing matter, conducting another study using a qualitative method gives a comprehensive, in-depth result that will enrich and complement the current knowledge on smoking in the Philippines and the meanings of smoking in general. Specifically, the study responded to the call of the recent study of Yamaguchi *et al.* (2021), which recommends conducting another qualitative investigation relative to the said topic. Inasmuch as varied and complex the meanings of smoking for the participants of the previous investigations, farmworkers' smoking attribution could likewise offer a unique insight that is vital in smoking prevention and cessation efforts for them as argued by Collins *et al.* (2002).

Theoretical Lens

Sociocultural Tradition

This study is anchored on sociocultural tradition, wherein communication is conceived as the (re)production of social order (Maguire, 2006). This tradition

foregrounds that reality and knowledge are socially constructed through micro level interaction processes (Maguire, 2006) and, thus, shared by individuals (Wang *et al.*, 2011). According to Moen (2006), it is one version of social constructivism that connects entities of mind and world. This tradition is aimed at looking at the important contributions of society to individual development and the interaction between people and the culture in which they live (Ameri, 2020).

One of the proponents of this tradition is Lev Vygotsky, a Russian psychologist, who accentuates that learning and development transpire on two planes: the social plane (interactions with others) and the psychological plane (within the individual) (Wang *et al.*, 2011). Vygotsky (1978) emphasizes that it is through socially and culturally shaped environments that human learning and development occur. Human development, including mental functioning, is heavily dependent on people's engagement in social activities given the situation that individuals interact with other people, objects, and events.

In this tradition, it can be inferred that social interaction has a fundamental role in human development as people engage in the discourse and socially construct what they jointly view as real. Consequently, people develop a sense of self by being around other people. The sociocultural lens enables us to find out how external factors affect people in perceiving themselves (Aboulafia, 2016) and making meanings of concepts and things around them, which consequently guide their actions. Wertsch (2000) emphasizes that action (e.g., smoking), including mental action, is shaped and reflected by sociocultural setting. Hence, there is a relationship between human action and social and cultural contexts.

Moreover, the sociocultural approach also looks at how a person's experiences, influences, and culture help shape why they act the way they do. In making sense of their experiences, people use narratives or stories as socioculturally situated tools (Philpott, 2014). In this study, which viewed the concept of smoking through the sociocultural lens, it is argued that how farmworkers regard or perceive smoking is primarily grounded on sociocultural factors, their experiences, and interactions with their environment. Through narrative approach, which has strong underpinning on sociocultural tradition (Moen, 2006), eliciting and analyzing farmworkers' stories or narratives is expected to give aid in exploring and extracting the farmworkers' meaning of smoking.

Philosophical Assumptions or Worldviews

This study takes on the social constructivist worldview as it fits well with the study's overall objectives – to make sense of and unpack the meanings that the participants have about smoking. In this worldview, which is usually complemented with interpretivism, "individuals try to explore understandings of the world in which they live and work. People develop subjective meanings of their experiences – meanings directed towards certain objects or things" (Creswell, 2007, p. 8). This particular worldview positions that meanings are different and complex formed through social interaction and individual's cultural and historical background. Hence, the present study focuses and relies mostly on the participants' views (e.g., of smoking) wherein subjective meanings are formed in social and historical settings.

Creswell (2007) underscores that qualitative research is described as interpretive research in which marginalized groups are represented. He emphasized

that in this type of research, the questions are directed towards topics and issues that generally target and serve the disadvantaged. The same case is closely akin to the present study, which seeks to shed light on a pressing issue involving the marginalized – smoking among farmworkers.

Using the interpretive lens of social constructivism, it was accentuated in this study that meanings of and associations to concepts and behavior, particularly smoking, vary from each individual formed by their experience and even cultural backgrounds. For this reason, meanings must be drawn upon the people.

Chapter 3

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study followed a qualitative research design. It is focused on generating knowledge from human experience (Sandelowski, 2004). Carried out in a natural setting, this inquiry process seeks to understand social or human problem based on building a complex holistic picture grounded on comprehensive views of the participants (Abdulai & Owusu-Ansah, 2014). According to Cresswell (2013), it is best to utilize this approach when an individual has a problem or issue needing to be explored to gain detailed understanding of it; intends to empower other individuals; and develops a theory. Hence, this methodology is appropriate in the present study as it created knowledge grounded on participants' experiences that helped them in associating meanings with a health issue – smoking. There are a baffling number of approaches under this methodology; however, the present study employed the narrative approach or inquiry to understand and capture the points of view of participants. Through the comprehensive nature of this approach, it was expected that the study's objectives would be addressed.

Narrative Approach

The narrative approach, also referred to as narrative inquiry, falls within the realm of social constructivism (Ntinda, 2019) and sociocultural tradition; it opines that through participation in social activities in the world, people learn and develop (Moen, 2006). This type of inquiry is geared towards revealing people's (the storyteller) meanings of their experiences (culture, historical experiences, identity, and lifestyle)

with emphasis on storied experience (Salkind, 2010). In other words, the narrative approach aims to unpack narratives or stories of people's lives, which they tell in their own words and grounded on their worlds (Kim & Latta, 2009; Riessman & Quinney, 2005). Hence, the stories themselves serve as the raw data (McAdams, 2009), which are obtained from small samples of participants or small groups (Salkind, 2010). Under this approach, the procedures yielding narrative data comprise interviews, which solicit stories and oral histories, and written autobiographies and biographies (Hoshmand, 2005).

Moen (2006) underscores that there are three claims or underpinnings about narrative research. First, human beings organize and make meanings of their experiences of the world through narratives they tell. Second, narrative researchers preserve that told stories depend on the individual's past and present experiences, their values, the audience of the stories being told to, the addressees, the timing and context or setting of the storytelling.

According to several scholars (Cresswell, 2013; Newby, 2014; Savin-Baden & Van Niekerk, 2007), utilizing the narrative approach in qualitative studies offers several advantages. First, eliciting stories from people, who are in-born storytellers, is more convenient since they are delighted to share and report their stories. Second, the accomplishment of gathering comprehensive data is easy since stories provide dense descriptions through narrated events. Third, the participants unravel themselves in their stories; hence, collecting in-depth meaning is highly possible. Lastly, the identification as to whether individuals have the habit of telling the truth becomes obvious through the data interpretation.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in Sitio Lalawan, Linabo, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, Philippines. A lowland and landlocked area, Sitio Lalawan is an approximately 45-minute drive away from the city proper. It is a farming community, wherein tenant farming system is commonly practiced and rice, corn, sugarcane, and vegetable are cultivated. Along with the aforementioned, farm labor is considered people's main source of living; they are usually paid at a minimum daily wage of Php 300. Almost half of the total population is constituted by Lumads from the Higaunon tribe – one of the seven ethnic groups of Bukidnon. The area is also inhabited by other groups, namely Ilonggo, Karay-a, Boholano, and Cebuano. Despite these cultural differences, the common language spoken is Bisaya or Cebuano. Binukid – the Lumad's language – is rarely used, except during rituals and when Lumad elders engage in a conversation with their constituents. The people's religion includes Roman Catholic, Seventh-day Adventist, Fundamental Baptist, and Pentecostal. Additionally, the Sitio has educational institutions: two elementary schools (public and private) and one public high school.

Participants of the Study

The participants of this study were farmworkers from the previously mentioned area. In quest of identifying possible distinct meanings of smoking, their work was particularly identified to make variations from the participants involved in the previous studies. If all possible, males were exactly chosen to further elaborate the findings of Yamaguchi *et al.* (2021) and Yen & Tan (2021), who found that Filipino men tend to be smokers than women. However, participation was also open to female smokers,

who were willing to take part in the study. Regardless of ethnicities (e.g., Lumad), culture and religion, those who would like to participate were welcome provided that they were adult smokers who were farmworkers.

Sampling Procedure

Purposeful sampling method was used in choosing the participants. Generally, purposeful sampling involves identifying and selecting individuals who are knowledgeable or experienced about the phenomenon of interest (Cresswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Along with this, the availability and willingness of the possible participants to participate, and their communication skills to share opinions should also be taken into consideration (Bernard, 2002). According to Palinkas *et al.* (2015), one commonly used purposeful sampling technique is criterion sampling, which selects participants based on the pre-determined criteria. In this study, the following criteria were used in choosing the participants: farmworker who 1) is a smoker, 2) lives in Sitio Lalawan, 3) is of legal age, 4) has been tilling the farm for at least five years, and 5) is willing and available to participate in the study.

According to Patton (2002), there are no rules in identifying the sample size in qualitative research. The guiding principle in this type of research is to sample only until data saturation is reached (Moser & Korstjens, 2018), which is also termed as “sampling to the point of redundancy.” The purpose of this present study is to provide maximum information on the phenomenon. Therefore, sampling was stopped when data saturation was achieved, that is no new information was forthcoming. Patton (2002) indicated that there is a need to have a minimum sample size and increase if necessary to data saturation; hence, the minimum sample size at seven was used in this present study.

Role of the Researcher

In this qualitative study, the researcher was directly involved in the different stages of the research process, namely thematizing, designing, interviewing, transcribing, analyzing, verifying, and reporting (Fink, 2000). He was the main instrument for the data collection and analysis; he interpreted the data and eventually, arrived at the participants' meanings of smoking. In an attempt to access the thoughts and feelings of the participants during the data collection (interview and storytelling), he paid close attention to their narratives. He encouraged them to share further by verbal cues (humming, giving affirmative statements, and asking clarifying questions) and nonverbal prompts (nodding, projecting facial expressions and adopting a position of attentive listening). Early in the interview, the researcher established rapport and trust with the participants. He treated them with highest respect and sensitivity in the entire session. In the data interpretation, the researcher's role was to build integrity throughout the process. He also veered away from the concept of "smoothing" – the tendency to entreat positive result that is way different from the exact data (Mertova & Webster, 2019). Safeguarding the participants' identity and data was the researcher's sole responsibility (Austin, 2015).

The researcher was born and raised in the research locale, which he considers his permanent address and where his family resides. Hence, he is quite acquainted with the ways of life of the participants. However, he laid aside his biases and assumptions about them (if there were any) that might have negatively affected the overall results of the study.

Data Collection Procedures

A list of farmworkers was sought from the Malaybalay City Agriculture Office in the Province of Bukidnon. From the list, prospective participants were matched based on the criteria set. Necessary permission from the Barangay Office to conduct the study was then obtained by sending a formal letter (Annex A). After which, an invitation letter along with the consent form (Annex B) was given to the identified participants. They were also informed about the purpose and the scope of the study. Before the interview and storytelling session, the sociodemographic profiles of the participants were obtained.

The dates of the data collection were scheduled according to the participant's preference and availability. The original plan was to conduct an online interview because of the pandemic. However, because some farmworkers have no gadgets and there was no longer border restriction, face-to-face interview through storytelling were instead done. It was assured that all the participants chosen were vaccinated and minimum public health standards required by the DOH were strictly followed.

As a form of appreciation, the researcher gave them a simple token (food packs) to compensate for the time they shared during the interview and storytelling session.

Research Instrument

Storytelling

In this study, the data was obtained through storytelling – a basic form of communication that is commonly used to convey ideas, values, identity, and culture

(Palacios *et al.*, 2015). Commonly employed in narrative inquiry, storytelling is utilized by participants as their means of communicating their realities (Wang & Geale, 2015). It is likewise employed by researchers to elicit information from people and understand their subjective experiences (Scholander *et al.*, 2021). It can aid researchers in throwing light on the meaning that individuals associate with a specific circumstance. Storytelling can also support researchers in exploring the world from the perspective of the participants, especially those coming from vulnerable populations (Palacios *et al.*, 2015) (i.e., farmworkers in the present study). In this premise, the researcher himself served as the research instrument for data collection in this study – that is, eliciting detailed narratives or stories from the participants. It was through his facilitative interaction that a conversational space was constructed: this space is an arena where the participants feel safe to share stories about their experiences and life-worlds (Pezalla *et al.*, 2015). To achieve this, he allowed the participants to tell freely their stories about smoking grounded on their experiences. Correspondingly, he carefully listened to their narratives and asked probing, validating or follow-up questions during the session.

Collection of Stories

The narrative methodology focuses on an open style of interviewing, which enables the participants to express themselves freely (Artioli *et al.*, 2019). Following the procedure of Stott & Priest (2018) and the advice of Scheffelaar *et al.* (2021) in collecting stories, the unstructured interview or open interview was employed to enable participants to structure their story of smoking experience and circumstances, and motivations that shape their actions. As an introduction to the open narrative interview, the researcher told the participants “*I am interested in hearing your story about your*

smoking experience, particularly regarding the situations when you need to smoke.”

Follow-up questions were then thrown at them when there were points from their answers needing elaboration and clarification. Further questions were also asked when necessary to expand on a part of their story or to fill in a gap thereon (Stott & Priest, 2018) by following the wording, ordering, and phrasing of the participants (Scheffelaar *et al.*, 2021). The entire duration of the interview and storytelling session that lasted from 18-45 minutes was audio-taped for documentation and data analysis.

Data Analysis Procedures

In this study, the two-phase data analysis was employed. The first phase was the restorying introduced by Ollerenshaw & Creswell (2002) and the second one was the narrative thematic analysis of Riessman (2008). In analyzing the original raw data from the transcript, restorying is highly important in getting the main point of the story, observing continuity, and ensuring that it follows a chronological sequence (beginning, middle, and end) just like how a novel is written (Ollerenshaw & Creswell, 2002). In the present study, restorying was vital in determining how the farmworkers tell and make sense of their experiences, which shape their understanding of smoking and consequently define and guide their actions. On the other hand, the narrative thematic analysis helped in finding emergent themes, which represent the meaning of smoking among the farmworkers derived from individual stories. Additionally, the narrative thematic analysis provided aid in presenting the findings in the results section by organizing them according to their common themes accompanied by stories or excerpts thereof.

Restorying

Restorying is the process of collecting and analyzing stories based on vital elements of the story like time, place, plot, and scene (Foxall *et al.*, 2021). Also, restorying is based on narrative elements, namely the problem, characters, setting, actions, and resolution (Ollerenshaw & Creswell, 2002). This will then be followed by composing the story in chronological sequence (Nardi, 2016). Oftentimes, individuals tell their stories differently; hence, this sequence is not followed and thus stories are illogically developed. However, this can be addressed by restorying in which the researcher fills in the missing link among ideas by collaborating with the participants. In the process of restorying the participant's story and reporting of themes, rich detail on the experiences' setting (friends, family, workplace, home, social organization, or school) where the story physically takes place is described by the researcher (Ollerenshaw & Creswell, 2002).

In this study, the problem-solution narrative approach in restorying, introduced by Ollerenshaw & Creswell (2002), was adopted. The process includes transcribing the audiotaped interview and storytelling session, reading and re-reading the transcripts to get a sense of the data, identifying the elements of plot structure (characters, setting, problem, actions, events/attempts, and resolution) by color-coding the transcripts, and lastly, sequencing the events for the transcript to make sense. Table 1 shows the overview of the problem-solution analysis while Figure 1 demonstrates the process of sequencing of events.

Table 1. Organizing the plot elements into the problem-solution narrative structure

Rough Transcription	Characters	Setting	Problem	Actions	Resolution
Code plot structure elements (color-highlight or insert element notation)	Individual's archetype, personality, behavior, style, and patterns	Context, environment, conditions, place, time, locale, year, and era	Question to be answered or phenomena to be described or explained	Movements through the story illustrating character's thinking, feelings, intentions, actions, and reactions, about failed and successful attempts	Answer the question and explains what caused the turning point or the character to change

Taken from Ollerenshaw & Creswell (2002) (p. 335)

Taken from Ollerenshaw & Creswell (2002) (p. 336)

Figure 1. Sequencing the events into the problem-solution narrative structure

Narrative Thematic Analysis

Narrative thematic analysis is the process of analyzing content within the text; hence, it is focused on what is said in the story rather than how the story is told (Riessman, 2008). Although it seeks common themes across the participants' accounts just like how the conventional thematic analysis is carried out, narrative thematic analysis prioritizes the narrative elements and retains a story sequence instead of coding the segments of text (Tarzia *et al.*, 2020).

In the present study, the aim of employing narrative thematic analysis was to interpret the meanings of smoking with respect to the farmworkers' stories and determine what each story was about, which is referred to by Riessman (2008) as the "point" of the story. Using narrative thematic analysis, farmworkers' stories were then analyzed to finally arrive at salient themes or categories, which represented the farmer's perceived meaning of smoking and their motivations in engaging themselves in smoking activity. When necessary, the stories with common plotlines were grouped into the same themes or categories (Tarzia *et al.*, 2020). The present study employed the five-phase narrative thematic analysis as shown in Table 2 (Riessman, 2008).

Table 2. The five-phase narrative thematic analysis

Phase no.	Activity
1	Organization and preparation of the data
2	Obtaining a general sense of the information
3	The coding process
4	Making categories or themes
5	Interpretation of the data

(1) Organization and preparation of the data included transcribing of audiotapes after the interview and storytelling session; however, this was bypassed since transcription of audiotapes was carried out in the first phase of restorying process. This step in narrative thematic analysis also comprised the removal of non-narrative lines such as casual conversation, replacement or deletion of participant's identifiers such as names and locations, and assigning fictitious names to each participant.

(2) During transcribing, obtaining a general sense of the information also happened – that is, familiarizing the data and taking down notes on the rudimentary patterns or themes.

(3) The coding process involved re-reading the transcripts and identification of recurring words, ideas, or patterns generated. Generating the initial codes was where meaningful and systematic data organization happened.

(4) Codes were then placed into a logical category – a word or phrase that described some segments of the explicit data from the transcripts.

(5) The interpretation of the data involved studying the categories and their corresponding codes. This was to determine whether there were any overarching themes or theories that provided insight into the meaning of smoking among the farmworkers. However, this was done simultaneously during the coding process.

Strategies for Validating Findings

Strategies in validating the findings include respondent validation coined by Cresswell & Clark (2011) as “member-checking.” In this process, the participants were invited to comment on the interview transcripts and examine whether the final themes

and concepts were produced sufficiently to mirror the phenomena being investigated (Long & Johnson, 2000). As this study were reviewed by the panel members, who are experts in the field of communication research, peer-debriefing was likewise utilized to establish the validity of the findings as this provided credibility to the study through the inputs of the reviewers (panel members).

Anticipated Ethical Issues

In the course of conducting this research, some unanticipated ethical issues may arise. To avoid this, the following ethical considerations were taken into account:

The research design is comprehensively described in the preceding sections. In terms of validity, it was assured that the results and conclusion of the study were interrelated with the research questions.

Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher obtained an approval from the panel. Before the data collection (open interviews and storytelling), the researcher likewise gained informed consent from the participants by signing a form, which was treated as the agreement between the two parties (researcher and the participants). The researcher verbally informed the participants about the details of the consent form. It is in this way that they could make informed decisions as to whether or not they would participate. Their participation was purely voluntary; hence, they were told that they could back out anytime at any stage without giving a reason and without cost or penalty. Also, it was ensured that the participants were not harmed by any means during the research process. Their personal information remained confidential – they were not written or indicated in this study and publish elsewhere. As for the data, it

was ensured that they were properly analyzed; no result was omitted that may cause misinterpretation among the readers (Jenn, 2006). Finally, the researcher had no conflict of interest with anyone, organizations, or institutions that might have affected the implementation of the study and the reporting of its results.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Farmworkers' Sociodemographic Profile

It was necessary to determine the sociodemographic information of the participants to ensure that they meet the sampling criteria set and to better understand their context. Hence, before the proper interview session (storytelling) commenced, relevant sociodemographic data were obtained from the farmworkers. Seven participants participated in the study. The youngest was 30 while the oldest was 55 (Table 3).

Table 3. Sociodemographic profile of the farmworkers

Pseudonym	Age	Sex	Highest educational attainment	Marital status	Ethnic group	Years in farm working	Estimated daily cigarette consumption	Smoking initiation
Anton	55	Male	High school graduate	Married	Ilonggo	36	2 packs	Teenage years
Ben	33	Male	High school graduate	Married	Ilonggo	10	2 packs	Teenage years
Caloy	30	Male	High school graduate	Married	Higaunon	10	1 pack	Teenage years
Dionicio	34	Male	High school graduate	Married	Higaunon	8	1 pack	Teenage years
Eduardo	37	Male	High school graduate	Married	Higaunon	22	2 packs	Teenage years
Felimon	33	Male	Elementary level	Single	Higaunon	33	10 sticks	Teenage years
Gibo	41	Male	High school level	Married	Cebuano	20	2 packs	Teenage years

All of them were male and mostly were high school graduates, married, and came from the Higaunon tribe. Their length of farm work ranged from 10 to 36 years. Farmworkers mostly consumed two packs of cigarettes every day. Based on the

classification made by Wilson *et al.* (1992), the farmworkers fall under heavy smokers since they puff cigarettes more than 25 cigarettes per day. Interestingly, all of them started smoking in their teenage years, which accords well with Reitsma *et al.* (2021), who found that smoking initiation occurred at ages that range from 14 to 25 years among young people in 204 countries. This trend was also observed by Barrington-Trimis *et al.* (2020), who found that the age of cigarette smoking initiation among young adults (aged 18-23 years) in the US doubled from 2002 (20.6%) to 2018 (42.6%).

Meanings of Smoking

This study aimed to extract the meanings of smoking among the farmworkers that consequently guided their actions. The meanings were unpacked from their narratives, which were collected using open interviews. The study viewed the topic at hand through the sociocultural lens. Hence, along with the research questions posted, sociocultural factors, shaping the participants' conceptualization of smoking, were also considered in the data interpretation and analysis, particularly in arriving at themes during the narrative thematic analysis. Although sociocultural factors were prioritized, some significant meanings outside the realm of socio-culturalism like psychological and environmental drivers that sprang from the analysis were also included in the findings to provide a thick description of the phenomenon (smoking) under exploration.

Restorying of the farmworkers' narratives yielded topical stories. They were then subjected to narrative thematic analysis, wherein the stories were categorized under a theme with reference to the main "point" of the stories and the similarities and differences of their plotlines. Interestingly, there were responses with no narrative structure or story elements that were essential in enriching a particular theme. Hence,

they were included in the narrative thematic analysis (see Annex C) and some interview excerpts were also included in this section. The findings illuminated various facets of meanings that emerged from the farmworkers' experiences with smoking. A total of five themes were arrived at, constituting the meaning of smoking among the farmworkers, namely a parent and peer's influence, a means to manage negative feelings and emotions, a thought provoker and organizer, a culture among friends, and an integral part of life.

A Parent and Peer's Influence

Parent's Influence

Two farmworkers reported histories of smoking; they started during their teenage years. In their responses, it was highlighted that the farmworkers identified factors like existing in social environments wherein they grew up as influential in their smoking initiation. In particular, living with parents who smoked and being surrounded by smoker peers were instrumental for starting and continuing to smoke. Although their parents did not directly tell them to do so, their exposure to their parents had given them subtle permission to engage in smoking activity. Also, their parents did not bat an eye on them when they were caught smoking for the first time. Consequently, this encouraged the farmworkers to begin and continue smoking with a preconceived idea that it was acceptable to smoke at their age. In Anton's (pseudonym) word, they "inherited" smoking from their ancestors.

"Murag nasunod man gud na sa among kaliwat. Akong mama ug papa mga manigarilyohay gyod to sila sa una. Maong katong gakakita nako nga gapanigarilyo sila, murag wala koy gakakita nga problema. Maong akong

gihunahuna nga okay ra diay manigarilyo, samot na nga di man sad sila gapabaya sa amoa unya gapaningkamot sad sila para mahatag among mga panginahanglan. Mao ganing pagkasapon nila sa akua nga gapanigarilyo, wala ko nila kasab-i. Niingon ra man gani sila nga 'hinay-hinaya lang kay gaeskuyla pa ka... Kung magdesisyon ka nga mupadayon aning bisyoha pareha sa amo, okay ra basta inyong pag-eskuyla, di lang nimo biyaan.' So okay ra gyod sa ilaha. Wala man ingon nga nakatilaw ko'g kasaba sa ila kay tungod ana, wala gyod. Human ato, naay mga higayon nga tagaan gyod ko's akong papa og duha ka stick, paipitan niya sa akong notebook ayha ko muadto'g eskuylahan kay di man lagi kapalit og sigarilyo, akong allowance kay gamay raman lagi sa una, piso, uno singkwenta, ana. Ako rang tultolon ang sigarilyo sa akong notebook kada buntag." (Anton)

["It seemed we inherited smoking from our descendants. My father and mother were smokers before. When I saw them smoking, I didn't see any problem. So I thought it was okay to smoke, especially since they took care of us and strived hard to provide for our needs. So by the time my parents caught me smoking, they didn't reprimand or scold me. Instead, they only said 'you take it slowly since you're still studying... if you decide to continue doing this vice just like what we do, it's okay as long as you don't take your studies for granted.' So, it was really okay for them. I didn't experience being scolded by them, never. After that confrontation, there were times that my father left me with two cigarettes in between the leaves of my notebook before I went to school since my allowance was only a peso or one peso and 50 centavos. I just looked for the cigarettes in my notebook every morning."]

From Anton's narrative, it can be observed how he highlighted that smoking can be traced back to his descendants. While he did not explain the detail about what he meant by "descendants," the next sentence could explain what it was about. He might be referring to his smoker parents to whom he linked his history of smoking. Seeing his parents' smoking behavior had shaped his understanding and belief that smoking was not a barrier to becoming responsible parents, thereby impinging on his mind that as long as a smoker performed his duties well in the family, it was okay to smoke. In his story, the concept of being a responsible family member was further signified when Anton's parents, upon discovering that he smoked, told him that he – who had responsibilities and duties as a student in the family at that time – could smoke on condition that he would do well in school. Interestingly, the responsible parenthood of Anton's parents, albeit being smokers, also extended not only to provide for their family's needs but also to support Anton's smoking behavior. This appeared in the narrative when his father, recognizing that Anton could not afford to buy cigarettes because of his inadequate allowance, gave him sticks of cigarettes before leaving for school.

Meanwhile, Eduardo (pseudonym) welcomed smoking to his life by observing his parents at their house when he was a teenager. In his narration below, he detailed their family's experience when they moved to a new place, where the presence of mosquitoes was ubiquitous, owing to the place's location and characteristics. As a result, his parents resorted to smoking to address this problem.

“Sa unang panahon, akong ginikanan manigarilyohay. Gakakita nako sila pirmi sa una nga gapanigarilyo tungod pod sa among sitwasyon sa Parang nga grabe kadagha’g lamok. Ako ra po’ng gisunod ilang gabuhaton kay ingon

pa nila, makawala lagi daw sa lamok. Maong gapanigarilyo pod ko aron di pod ko paakon sa lamok.” (Eduardo)

[“Back in the day, my parents were also smokers. I always saw them smoking before because of our situation in Parang, where there were a lot of mosquitoes. I also imitated what they were doing, because according to them, smoking can shove off mosquitoes. That’s why I also smoked so that mosquitoes wouldn’t bite me.”]

Eduardo recognized that the root cause of his parents’ smoking was primarily an environmental factor, particularly the mosquitoes. Consequently, this shaped Eduardo’s understanding of the good effects of smoking, which had the capacity to act as a mosquito repellent. This was further evidenced by how his parents articulated the benefits of smoking against those insects by telling him that “*smoking can shove off mosquitoes.*” This clearly meant that his parent’s remarks about smoking were powerful tools for influencing Eduardo’s good conception of smoking. It can also be said that it was through observing and modeling his parents, who frequently smoked at home, that made him decide to initiate smoking. When asked about the reaction of his parents when they saw him smoking for the first time, Eduardo answered, “*wala ko nila [ginikanan] gibawalan kay mga manigarilyohay man sad lagi sila... mao sad na’ng ilang namat-an sa ilang ginikanan.*” [*“they (parents) didn’t forbid me to smoke because they’re smokers themselves... that’s what they also saw from their parents before.”*] This implied that he had the confidence firmly built on his belief that his parents could not afford to reprimand him because doing so might appear to be an antithesis to his parents and grandparent’s identity as smokers. Eduardo recalled another previous event, wherein he smoked to drive away insects at work.

“Sa among maisan sa una, daghan kay’g insekto. Kanang magbasok-basok mi og mangabono sa bag-ong tubo nga mais, pirmi ko gapanigarilyo para mawala ang insekto. Samot na tong insekto nga galupad-lupad, katong ‘langi,’ nga gasulod sa atong mata og dalunggan. Maong kung wa mi sigarilyo, pirmi mi gasuot og masks. Kay kung dili, di gyod mi ka-concentrate sa among trabaho. Ingon pa gani sa akong papa nga mas maayo na’ng manigarilyo kay ang sigarilyo makapawala sa lamok.” (Eduardo)

[“On our corn farm before, there were a lot of insects. When we gleaned the weeds and put fertilizers on the young corn, I always smoked to shove off insects, especially those flying insect, the ‘langi,’ that goes into our eyes and ears. Those insects were a great disturbance at work. So if we don’t have a cigarette, we’d always put on our masks. Otherwise, we couldn’t concentrate at work. My father even told me that it was okay to smoke because the cigarette smoke helped the insects to go away.”]

In the abovementioned account of Eduardo, it was understood that he adopted his father’s technique, which was to smoke, in order to shoo away the insects while working on their corn farm. In this sense, he successfully modeled his father’s smoking behavior at work that subsequently benefited them through their livelihood. Furthermore, in the second narrative, Eduardo once again clearly ascribed his smoking continuation to his father because of the knowledge that his father shared with him – knowledge about the capacity of cigarette smoke to eliminate the presence of insects that affected their performance at work in particular and might put their livelihood at risk in general. Hence, it can be concluded that his parents, and even grandparents, had a huge effect on his positive conceptualization of smoking.

In this present work, the results showed that exposure to parents' smoking behavior at home had a major influence on how smoking was positively viewed by the farmworkers, leading to the modeling of smoking behavior. They thought that the smoking behavior of their parents, who have been cited in the literature as "role models" of healthy behaviors to their children (Coto *et al.*, 2019), was acceptable. Anton was exposed to his parents' smoking and he regarded them as responsible parent-smokers who did not neglect their family's needs and were even very supportive of his journey towards smoking maintenance. Therefore, his exposure, his belief about his parent as responsible smokers, and their support were key drivers that led Anton into the world of smoking. On the other side of the coin, Eduardo observed how his father successfully addressed the presence of mosquitoes that were a great nuisance at home by lighting cigarettes whose smoke permeated the air. In turn, Eduardo was able to replicate effectively his father's technique, which was to smoke, for the sake of their livelihood. In general, it can be understood that their narratives spoke about social factors, which were smoker parents, including grandparents, who had a major role in their positive conceptualization of smoking, which encouraged them to begin and continue smoking. They modeled the smoking behavior of their parents because they thought it was acceptable to smoke. Since farmworkers' parents were also smokers themselves, their parents could not afford to reprimand them as doing so would be futile – that is, not practicing what they preached. In sum, parent's influence on farmworkers' smoking initiation and continuation was manifested through their exposure to their smoker parents, their parents' identity as smokers, modeling their parents' smoking behavior, and the explicit and implicit support from their parents to their smoking journey.

These results agreed with the findings of earlier reports. In a study by Wilkinson *et al.* (2008), it was found that parent smokers directly influenced smoking behavior and their children reported positive attitudes towards smoking. Strunin *et al.* (2017) and Okoli *et al.* (2017) forwarded that those family members who smoked promoted the initiation of smoking and at the same time influenced the earlier onset of smoking in adolescents. In a similar vein, the study of Johnston *et al.* (2012) demonstrated that the parents were considered by indigenous Australian youths as “teachers” of smoking because of the latter’s exposure to tobacco at home and smoking paraphernalia. The same case applies to American-Indian adolescents, who modeled their smoking behavior on their parents (Kegler *et al.*, 2015). It was also highlighted by Baheiraei *et al.* (2014) that a family member who smokes was associated with lifetime cigarette use among Iranian male adolescents.

Peer’s Influence

Four farmworkers gave accounts about how they were influenced by their friends to smoke. During the interview, they revealed that alongside parental influence, smoker peers also persuaded them to smoke for the first time. Gibo’s (pseudonym) friends told him to “try” it. Correspondingly, Anton emphasized, “*tanan man gyod moinom, mosigarilyo. Makaimpluwensya gyod ang barkada. Kay kung unsa imong makita sa imong barkada, masunod gyod nimo.*” [“*all were drinking, smoking. Friends were also influential. Because what you see from your friends, you always follow.*”] As such, he was able to share a story about how his father became a smoker because of his father’s older friends, who served as his teachers on the subject of smoking.

“*Sa una, akong lolo daghan og kabaw. Maong iyang sugoon akong papa, katong grade 1 pa siya, nga manigway sayo sa buntag. Didto dayon niya*”

matagbuan iyang mga barkada nga mga gulang-gulang sa iya, unya tudloan siya unsaon paghimo ug pagpanigarilyo anang linikit nga tabako. Daghang mga higayon nga akong papa di na mangeskuyla tungod ana. Mao nang nahimo na dayong smoker akong papa.” (Anton)

[“Before, my grandfather had a lot of carabaos. That’s why he’d always ask my father, who was in grade 1, to move the carabaos into the pasture early in the morning. There my father would meet his childhood friends, who were older than him, and taught him how to make and smoke a roll-hand cigarette. There were times that my father wouldn’t be able to go to school because of that. So that’s how my father became a smoker.”]

It can be observed that in the case of Anton’s father, it was also the trust of his grandfather in Anton’s father to take charge of the carabaos every morning that gave Anton’s father an opportunity to spend time with his friends on the pasture. Thus, the older friends of Anton’s father were given the chance to teach him about the means to smoke. Although it was not highlighted why his father followed the lead of his older friends, one major reason could be his father’s intent to be accepted into the group, even at the expense of his education. Anton also shared his story of how he was influenced by his high school friends to smoke.

“Katong hayskol pa ko, nakabarkada ko’g mga manginomay ug manigarilyohay pareha anang Juan [pseudonym] nga naa gapuyo karon diha’s pikas barangay. Ila kung gitagaan og sigarilyo, ingon sila ‘tilawi ni kay total laki man ta ug mao mani atong kinabuhi. Imong papa manigarilyohay pod.’ Kada tingpaniudto, kanang human mi’g paniudto, moinom mi ug manigarilyo sa

tindahan nilang Neneng [pseudonym]. Pagbalik ana's klasi mga ala-una, aw sakto na kaayo among karga.” (Anton)

[“When I was in high school, I became friends with smokers and alcohol drinkers like Juan (pseudonym) who now lives in the neighboring barangay. They offered me a cigarette by saying ‘you should try this because we’re men and this is our way of life. Your father is also a smoker.’ Every lunch break, after we ate our lunch, we’d go to Neneng’s (pseudonym) sari-sari store to drink and smoke. So when the classes resumed at 1 PM, we had already enough.”]

The story above depicted what was previously brought out by Anton that “because what you see from your friends, you always follow.” Although Anton’s high school friends were also found to be influential in his smoking initiation, it can also be inferred that his friends used his father, who was a smoker, as a point of reference that smoking was a masculine behavior and that smoking was acceptable as it is their way of life as men, just like what was characterized by Anton’s father through smoking. In other words, his friends pointed to his father as an example of men’s normal embodiment of cigarette smoking. Therefore, the image of his father as a smoker was also crucial as to how his friends viewed smoking that they consequently employed to encourage Anton to smoke. Meanwhile, Ben (pseudonym) also narrated an event about how his friends introduced smoking to him.

“Atong ulitawo pa ko, gipailaila ko’s akong mga barkada sa sigarilyo. Kapila gyod ka beses nga ila ko’ng testingan og tudlo pero wa gyod ko. Wa gyod ko nagpatintal. Dayon niabot sa time nga akong gitestingan sa balay nga wala sila kay gakatingala ko. Hangtod nga naadik ko. Gapangitaon na pirmi sa

akong ginhawa, unya nagsugod na dayon ko'g uban-uban sa akong mga barkada.” (Ben)

[“When I was still a teenager, my friends introduced me to cigarette smoking. There were several times that they tried to teach me how to do it but I declined. I was not tempted. Until such time that I tried it myself at home, without their presence, out of curiosity. Eventually, I got addicted to it. I always looked for it and then started to bond with my friends.”]

Interestingly, Ben asserted that it was not his smoker friends who influenced him to smoke despite their incessant offers to do so. Rather, it was out of his curiosity that drove him to try a cigarette. After several attempts, he eventually developed an intense sense of liking for it, terming the phenomenon as an “addiction.” During the interview, Ben always emphasized that it was not his friends who caused him to start smoking. While it might be true that it was his curiosity that was responsible for his smoking initiation, however, it can also be ascribed to his friends. Perhaps, the fact that he had always been going out with them and frequently exposed to the smoke gradually developed his curiosity. It could be that because of his exposure to them, he eventually got interested why they liked to smoke and what was in the cigarette that they loved and enjoyed about. This analysis was evinced in the response of Dionicio (pseudonym), who stated, *“kay gapanigarilyo man lagi sila [barkada], gakatingala sad ko unsay lami so ila ko'ng gitintal nga mutesting so ako sang gitestingan. Unya pila ka mga higayon, akong na-realize nga lami man diay. So didto dayon nagsugod tanan.”* [*“because they (friends) were smokers, I was always curious what it tasted like so they tempted me to try it so I tried it. After some time, I realized that it tasted good. So that's where it all started.”*] Under this circumstance, there is an indirect temptation that the

farmworkers experienced when being exposed to friends who they frequently saw smoking when they were together. As a result, the farmworkers became inquisitive of what they observed in their peers, thereby pushing them to try smoking and later on, realizing that it was pleasurable as what was highlighted by the farmworkers. In other words, one major social factor that influenced them to smoke was the direct and indirect peer pressure that they experienced when they were with their smoker friends. On one hand, the direct pressure was manifested when their peers told or encouraged them verbally or by offering them to try cigarettes. On the other hand, the indirect pressure was their exposure to smoke and smell of cigarettes when they were with their friends, which eventually stemmed curiosity, leading to smoking experimentation and initiation. Subsequently, their curiosity was satisfied by realizing and experiencing firsthand the same enjoyment and pleasure that their peers experienced when smoking, leading to smoking continuation and maintenance. In a nutshell, peer influence was characterized by direct and indirect peer pressures.

The present results agreed with Johnston *et al.* (2012), who explained that at this age, there was an increase of the influence of friends and social networks on smoking initiation and behavior among young people since they imposed social pressure on their peers to smoke in order to fit in or be accepted in the group. Johnston *et al.* (2012) expounded that this was the time when smoking experimentation frequently happens.

A Means to Manage Negative Feelings and Emotions

In their narratives, six farmworkers revealed some psychological aspects of smoking by punctuating its mental and emotional therapeutic benefits. Most of them utilized cigarettes as a way to cope with negative feelings and emotions like

anxiousness, tiredness, hate, irritation, loneliness, boredom, and nervousness. They smoked as self-medication to overcome these bad feelings and emotions. Most of their responses showed that smoking happened at work. Caloy (pseudonym) recalled an experience wherein he fell back on smoking when was caught in a stressful or shocking situation while he was working on the farm. It was when his sickle accidentally slightly cut his little finger while harvesting rice. Notice how he was able to surmount this perceived nerve-wracking situation.

“Kanang mag-harvest mo’g humay kay dapat paspas ka aron inyong grupo makauli og sayo unya di na dayon mo mainitan. Kay dali-dali lagi mi, naa toy time nga nasamad akong kumingking sa galab. Gikulbaan ko’g ayo ato kay grabe ang dugo. Gikulbaan ko’g samot katong giignan ko’s akong kauban nga ‘hala, nangluspada na ka, Caloy!’ Layo ang health center sa among gigalaban ato. Gitabangan dayon ko’s akong kauban, unya nangayo dayon ko’g sigarilyo aron makalma ko. Nikalma-kalma sad akong gibati samtang gayupyop og sigarilyo. Ila dayon ko’ng giignan nga muadto’s health center aron malimpyohan ug madresingan akong samad. Katong giignan ko’s midwife nga ‘hala, kadako ba aning imong samad!’ gikulbaan nasad ko, samot na tong iya nang gibutnga’g alcohol akong samad; grabe ka sakit. Katong nakauli na ko’s balay, naa pa gyapoy sakit kanang murag gaugtok-ugtok bitaw. Mao tong nanigarilyo nasad ko aron malimtan nako nga naa koy samad. Sa akong hunahuna, ang sigarilyo gyod ang nakatabang ato aron makalma ko.” (Caloy)

[“Manual harvesting of rice requires that you should be fast so that your group can go home early and escape from the scorching heat of the sun. Since we’re in hurry, there was a time when my sickle accidentally slightly cut the nail

of my little finger. I got so nervous because it was bleeding heavily. I got more nervous when one of my companions said that 'oh my, you looked pale, Caloy!' The health center was too far away from our location. I was then assisted by one of my companions and asked him to give me cigarettes so that I could calm down. I got slightly calmed while puffing my cigarettes. They then told me to go to the health center and have the wound cleaned and dressed. When the midwife saw my wound, she told me, 'oh, your wound is quite large!' So, I got nervous again, all the more when she poured alcohol on my wound; it was really painful. When I got home, the pain was still there it was like there was a beating sensation. So I smoked again to calm myself and for me to forget that I had a wound. I think smoking was the one that really helped me calmed."]

In his story, there were a lot of forces that contributed to his major problem, which was anxiousness due to his wound. First, it was his greatest desire to finish his work early for him to escape his major enemy at work, which was the scorching heat of the sun. The second was that, instead of finishing his work ahead of time, he accidentally sustained a wound. Because of this, he then became anxious, which was exacerbated by the surrounding people's verbal messages about his physical condition and the location of the farm from the health center. He could have thought that it would take him time to get treated, thereby prolonging his agony. To temporarily contain his anxiousness about his situation, it can be inferred that he used smoking as his coping mechanism. In his story, it was shown that smoking had a calming effect. He recognized beforehand that for him, smoking had the capacity to act as a medicine to manage his negative feeling. For this reason, he asked for it from his fellow farmworkers the moment he could no longer handle his emotional state. In the last part of his story, he highlighted that he utilized smoking as his temporary escape from

his present reality, especially when he articulated that he smoked for him to forget about the wound that fueled his anxiousness. If we look at it closely, there was an imbalance between his adversity and his ability to grapple with it. The imbalance was manifested by the “nervousness” or anxiousness that stemmed from his wound, which was worsened by the people around him and their physical location. This imbalance was termed by Beutel *et al.* (2018) as psychosocial stress, which, according to them, can influence smoking behavior. In the following statements, another two farmworkers shared instances when they usually smoked at work.

“Gapanigarilyo ko kanang gatrabaho ko’s uma, pareha anang diha’s basakan. Mainitan man ka ana unya ang trabaho kay pwersahanay gyod. Maong ganahan dayon ko manigarilyo. Kanang mopahulay mi sa buntag ug hapon ug kanang tingpaniudto samtang makarelaks na mi, tsada gyod kaayo sa paminaw ug kanang makahatag siya’g kusog kanang masuyop nakong aso.”
(Ben)

[“I smoke when I’m doing farm labor, just like in the rice field. You’re exposed to the heat of the sun and the work requires a lot of strength. That’s when I crave a cigarette. During morning and afternoon breaks and lunchtime when we (fellow farm laborers) can relax, it feels good and reinvigorating every time I inhale the smoke.”]

“Hmm, kanang musakit na akong likod [samtang gatrabaho sa uma], sakit na akong hawak. Kung mutindog ko, manigarilyo ko. Ug pagpahulay dayon. Di man sad maayo nga manigarilyo ka samtang gapala ka’s pilapil kay di man ka kaginhawa ana. Mao nang ayha ra ko gapanigarilyo kung tingpahulay

na. Kung makapahulay na ko gamay, mokuha na dayon ko ana'g sigarilyo ug manigarilyo na dayon sa kilid.” (Dionicio)

[“Hmm, when my back aches (while working on the farm), my hip already hurts. When I stand, I also smoke. And then rest. It’s not good to smoke while you’re shoveling the rice dikes because it suffocates you. That’s why I smoke when it’s already rest time. When my body is quite rested, I then pick cigarette and smoke there on the side.”]

It cannot be denied that farm working is physically arduous. Oftentimes, the farmworkers were exposed to the scorching heat of the sun. As a result, the farmworkers amassed mental and physical exhaustion during and after working. They needed to sustain their strength throughout the day to carry on their tasks. Therefore, farmworkers availed themselves of cigarettes and rest to regain their strength as revealed by their narratives. The relaxing and pleasurable feelings may be translated into the reinvigorating effect of smoking among the farmworkers. The farmworkers recognized that cigarettes had the power to re-energize them to get through the day. Hence, it can also be understood that the working environment and the nature of their work were contributing factors to their exhaustion, wherein cigarettes found their place to urge the farmworkers to smoke. Smoking may also be attributed to their socioeconomic status. These farmworkers’ jobs only earned lesser compared with the other type of jobs. Perhaps, they were using cigarettes to make their stomach full, especially since they mentioned that they smoked during morning, lunch, and afternoon breaks. Maybe, what they ate during breakfast and breaks was not enough for them to sustain the energy that was needed to perform their jobs. Therefore, in lieu of food, they consumed cigarettes instead to be full.

While the abovementioned accounts mostly talked about psychosocial stresses emanating from work environment, there were also farmworkers who spoke that they smoked during stressful situations, wherein the major contributing factors were family conflicts and relationship problems. Anton shared during the interview that after graduating high school, he was not able to go to college because his parents prioritized his older siblings. Because of that, he felt that there was favoritism in the family. Since he did not continue schooling, his parents entrusted all the farm that they cultivated. At a young age, he eventually became the breadwinner of the family. He supported the needs of his parents and his older and younger siblings. Anton narrated an incident wherein he got stressed over a family problem, specifically about his older sibling, who frequently rode on their parent's coattails.

“Naa koy magulang nga pirmi ra’g salig sa akong ginikanan. Kada harvest, pirmi na siya mangayo sa iyang bahin bisag way tabang-tabang. Kabalo mana sila [pamilya] nga problematic ko tungod ana. Mao nang pirmi ra ko gapuyoay sa bilyaran unya magdula didto. Samtang sige’g dugkal, sige sad ko’g sigarilyo og inom ug mag-uli na dayon ko ana mga ala-una sa kaadlawon. Pagmata nako ana’s alas-singko, ako na dayong bisitahon akong kabaw, baka, ug kabayo... padayon trabaho, ug bisita dayon sa uma. Kung paminaw nako, human na tanan akong trabaho, balik nasad dayon ko ana’s bilyaran. Naa gani toy time nga katong sige na ko’g balik-balik, mura na’g akong balay ang bilyaran, kung aha didto na ko gatulog. Kay maluluy-on man sad lagi akong inahan ug murag kabalo sad siya’s akong giagian, iya sad ko’ng dal-an og pagkaon didto’s bilyaran kay di na man ko gauli.” (Anton)

[“I have an older sibling who always depended on my parents’ help. In every harvest, he’d always ask for his share even if he didn’t bother to help. I became problematic and stressed because of that. They (family members) all knew that I was problematic. That’s why I always stayed at the nearest small billiard hall and played there. While I was stroking the ball, I also smoked heavily and drank liquor and I would then go home at 1 AM. When I woke up at 5 AM, I would then visit my carabao, cow, and horse... resume working, and visit the rice field. If I felt that I already finished my work, I would go to the billiard hall again. There was a time when this incident became a repetitive activity, so much so that the hall became my house, where I slept. My mother, who was very compassionate and knew what I was going through, would even bring me food at the billiard hall because I had not been going home.”]

In Anton’s story, it can be assumed that for Anton, performing one’s responsibility as a family member was a key to maintaining a harmonious family relationship. He expected that his sibling should have been the one supporting his parents by any means instead of the latter, especially since they were old, and as a way of paying back to them, who sent his sibling to college. Also, Anton knew that his parents could no longer work to sustain their personal needs, much more in supporting his other siblings’ necessities. Because of this, Anton became problematic, and he expected to be noticed by his family for possible resolution since he believed they knew about what he was feeling. As a means to de-stress, he made himself invisible at home by going to the billiard hall, wherein playing billiards, drinking, and smoking were his sources of sympathy. Despite that, he did not fail to perform his duties in the family as the breadwinner, that is by still working on the farm and taking care of their animals. In this sense, it can be perceived that smoking was one of Anton’s ways,

along with playing and drinking, to get through stress that was occasioned by a family conflict. In a similar vein, a family issue was also cited by Ben as the main agent of his hatred towards his father. He shared the following story:

“Adtong hayskol pa ko, akong papa kay sugarol. Mao nang ang kwarta unta nga para magamit sa among panginahanglanon ug sa among pag-eskuyla, mahurot niya pirmi sa bulangan. Kabalo na ka aning daghan ta’g igsuon nga kailangan niya suportaan. Naglagot gyod ko niya ato, ug dali ra kaayo ko gasaputon tungod anang iyang sugal. Ato nga time, sige ko’g sigarilyo aron mawala akong kasuko sa iya. Usahay muadto ko’s balay sa akong barkada, mosigarilyo, ug matulog dayon didto og mga pila ka adlaw. Gaapason gani ko’s akong mama didto. Nakahuman ko’g hayskol nga ako-ako lang, pareha anang mang-labor. Pero wa na ko nakapadayon sa college kay tungod sa problema’s kwarta.” (Ben)

[“Back when I was still in high school, my father was a gambler. That’s why the money which could have been used for our daily needs and my schooling was instead betted on cockfighting. You know, I have a lot of siblings who he should support. I really hated him and got easily irritated because of his gambling. That time, I always smoke to relieve my hate to him. Sometimes, I went to my friend’s house, smoke, and sleep there for days. My mother even fetched me there. I graduated high school through self-support, like doing farm labor. But I didn’t pursue college because of financial problems.”]

Ben recognized the significant role of his father, being the breadwinner of the family, in his and his siblings’ aspirations in life. In his story, it can be surmised that he expected his father to be responsible by supporting them financially, which his father

could really comply with. Ben assumed that his father's support was his ticket towards finishing college, thereby helping his family to get out of poverty. However, his father's gambling activity hampered this expectation. Hence, this developed irritation and hatred on the part of Ben, who then resorted to smoking and visiting his friends. In this respect, it can be said that Ben used smoking and absence at home to manage his hatred and irritation towards his father. Perhaps, he could not afford to lose his relationship with this father; hence, instead of fighting against him or telling bad about him, Ben smoked to suppress his ill feelings towards his father. This was in agreement with a previous study that yielded results stating that people with an angry disposition are more susceptible to nicotine's calming effect (Gehricke *et al.*, 2013). Another family conflict was cited by Eduardo, who also used smoking as a coping strategy to deal with his stress.

"Naa toy time nga grabe ko ka-stress tungod sa family trouble. Ulitawo pa ko ato. Tungod ato, hapit nagbulag akong mga ginikanan. Kada mag-away na sila's balay, moadto dayon ko's uma ana nga ako ra isa, unya grabe dayon akong sigarilyo ana para mawala akong stress ug aron di nako madumduman ang problema. Bisag temporary ra, mao nala'y akong gipili pod kay wa man koy lain maestoryahan sa akong problema. Gakaulaw sad ko'g estorya ato sa akong mga barkada." (Eduardo)

["There was a time when I was so stressed because of family trouble. I was teenager back then. Because of that, my parents were on the verge of separating. Every time they quarrel at home, I would always visit our farm alone and smoke there intensely to get away from stress and to forget about the problem. Although the relief was just temporary, I resorted to it because I didn't

have someone to share my problem with. I was also shy to talk about it to my friends.”]

Eduardo’s story showed how he loved his family as the conflict between his father and mother badly affected him. This family conflict created a stressful environment, wherein he may have overheard his parents’ frequent or intense fighting. He was also perturbed over the fact that his parents might separate because of that trouble. It can be seen that this caused him to get stressed, which took a toll on his physical and psychological well-being. Albeit recognizing the temporary relief brought about by smoking, Eduardo turned to it because he could not talk with friends about what he was going through. In this sense, the role of cigarette was also viewed as his emotional outlet wherein he could vent out his stress – just like the role of a friend, whom he could have shared his problems with and subsequently eased his burdened heart. In the extant literature, family conflicts have been found to be associated with smoking behavior among adults and even adolescents (Buhelt *et al.*, 2021; Lawless *et al.*, 2015; Šabić & Mujanović, 2020). Aside from farm labor, Caloy was also able to work on a poultry farm, tasked to maintain and fix the chicken coop or poultry house.

“Naa toy mga higayon nga nakatrabaho ko’s poultry-han, tig-maintain anang kulongan sa manok. Didto gapandayon namong salog nga kawayan samot na’g gakalata ug humok na na’ng kawayan. Giasayin man mi [kauban sa trabaho] kada sudlanan. Pananglitan lugar, ang isa ka tao iasayin sa una ug ikaduha nga kulongan, ug ang isa nasad sa ikatulo ug upat. Maong wa gyod koy lain maestorya-estoryahan kada tingpahulay na. Grabe gyod ka laay. Gitestingtan nako’g kawala akong kalaay pinaagi’s pagtan-aw anang gapangitlog nga mga manok. Pero kadugayan nakong tan-aw ana, sumo man

sad. Para mawala gyod siya, nikuot ko'g sigarilyo sa akong bolsa ug ako dayong gisindihan. Mao nang gadaladala gyod ko pirmi'g sigarilyo kay kung laayon ko, naa koy ma yupyop para mawala siya.” (Caloy)

[“There were instances when I worked on a poultry farm as coop maintainer. There I fixed the bamboo floor, especially when the bamboos were rotten or fragile. We were individually assigned in each cage. For example, one person was assigned to cages 1 and 2 and another one to cages 3 and 4. So, I didn't have anyone to talk to because we were apart. I was really bored during breaks. I tried to vanish the boredom away by watching the hens laying eggs. But looking at them for a long time could be very boring. To completely get rid of it, I picked up cigarettes in my pocket and lit them. That's why I always bring cigarettes with me because whenever I'm bored, I can have something to puff to brush it off.”]

In Caloy's experience, it was understood that his working location being away from his companions caused his boredom. He longed for the presence of someone to whom he could talk during breaks. He tried to employ other means to keep his boredom away like watching the hens laying eggs. However, it was the cigarette that completely obliterated the said feeling. This meant that he used cigarettes as his companion in the absence of his workmates. It was seen that smoking was his optimum option to curtail his boredom. Sweger (2021) wrote that in a study conducted by the Penn State College of Medicine, increased use of cigarettes is attributed to boredom. Consistent with this finding are those of Popova *et al.* (2021), who demonstrated that smokers engaged more frequently in smoking activity because of boredom, along with stress. Meanwhile, Felimon (pseudonym) imputed his loneliness

to the absence of his smoker friends who were already married and had only little to no time for their gatherings. So every time he smoked, he felt like he had a “barkada” (“friend”) with him.

“Kauban gyod nako na ang pagpanigarilyo kay ako ra pirmi diri’s uma. Kibale, ako siyang gitrato nga barkada ba. Sa una katong ulitawo pa ko, daghan kay ko’g mga barkada nga nagtudlo sa ako unsaon pagpanigarilyo. Grabe mi ka-enjoy sige’g uban sa una. Karon nga halusa sa ila kay minyo na man unya ako kay wa pa, usahay nalang mi gakita. Pirmi nako sila mahunahunaan kung manigarilyo ko. Paminaw nako naa sad koy kauban diri bisan pa’g ako ra usa.”

(Felimon)

[“Smoking is my companion because I’m always alone here on the farm. I treat it like a friend. Before when I was a teenager, I had a lot of friends, who taught me how to smoke. We enjoyed each other’s company. Now that most of them are married and I’m still single, we seldom see each other. I can always think of them when I smoke here. I feel like I have also companions here even if I’m just alone.”]

In Felimon’s narration, time was cited as his major enemy – that is, the time that his friends could no longer give him because of conflicting priorities. Perhaps, he might be thinking that they were the ones who were responsible for his bad feeling because they brought him into the smoking world and now, they left him alone and hanging. Hence, Felimon experienced social isolation and loneliness, which prompted him to smoke. It can be said that he regarded smoking as his friend with whom he previously and frequently shared the same environment. To put it simply, smoking made him feel the physical presence of his friends. Felimon might also be using

cigarette as his partner in life, considering that he has not been married yet compared with his friends, who might now be enjoying the companionship of their respective partners and families. That is to say, for him, smoking was tied to the identity of his friends. Philip *et al.* (2022) revealed that there existed a strong association between smoking and increasing social isolation and loneliness in older adults, suggesting that smoking as a prosocial is a misconception. This might also be true in the case of Felimon, who, later in his life, experienced loneliness because of smoking, which was primarily influenced by his friends who were now invisible in his life. Overall, the farmworkers used cigarettes to manage their negative feeling and emotions, namely stress, tiredness, hatred, irritation, boredom, loneliness, and hunger among others, which originated from working environment, family conflicts, socioeconomic status and absence of friends or companions.

A Thought Provoker and Organizer

Smoking helped four farmworkers in organizing their thoughts and ideas, especially in situations wherein they were caught with confusion at work and had problems with their livelihood. Gibo shared, “*usahay kanang magplano-plano ka ba unya kanang mag trabaho. Makatabang na’ng sige ka’g suyop samtang gaplano. Linaw kaayong panghunahuna.*” [“*sometimes when making plans and then while working. It can help when you make plans while puffing. It clears my mind.*”] In this context, they used smoking to improve their brain function. Apart from being a farmworker, Dionicio was also a *habal-habal* driver. Sometimes, when there was a problem with his motorcycle, he fixed it by himself. He recalled an incident wherein he was having a hard time putting back the parts of the motorcycle engine, which he had accidentally dismantled.

“Naa toy insidente nga galisod ko’g ayo sa makina’s akong motor. Natangtang nako kalit ang isa ka piyesa unya galisod ko’g balik ba. Di gyod nako siya mabalik hangtod nga gakaalit nako. Gitawagan pa gani nako sa cellphone akong amigo nga mekaniko pero di nako siya gakacontact kay hinay kaayong signal. Mao tong nagpahulay ko kadiyot unya sindi dayon ko’g isa ka sigarilyo. Gasigarilyo ko samtang gatan-aw sa akong natangtang nga piyesa sa makina. Human nako’g panigarilyo, kalit ra dayon nako nadumduman kung giunsa nako sa una. Ingon ko nga, ‘ay, oo, inanion raman diay to pagbalik ho.’ Akong dayo’ng gitapok tanan ug gitaud balik. Sa akong hunahuna, murag nakatabang gyod sa ako ang sigarilyo ato nga time. Nakatabang siya nga makahunahuna ko’g tarong.” (Dionicio)

[“There was this incident wherein I had a hard time fixing my motorcycle’s engine in our house. I accidentally dismantled one of its parts and had a hard time putting it back again. I couldn’t really fix it to the point that I got angry. I even called my friend over the phone but I couldn’t reach him because of a poor signal. So I took a rest for a while and lit one stick of cigarette. I was smoking and watching the dismantled pieces of the engine. After I finished smoking, I suddenly remembered how I did it before. I said, ‘oh, yes, this is how I should do it.’ I gathered all the pieces and assembled them again. I think during that time, smoking helped me with my problem. It helped me think well.”]

Dionicio’s story spoke about how he was able to solve his problem with his motorcycle, which was also one of their main sources of income. He tried to find other means to fix it. After realizing that he could no longer do it, he tried to ask for help from his friend, who was a mechanic, by calling him over the phone but Dionicio could not

reach him because of a poor signal. Hence, he rested and lit cigarettes, and then suddenly, he had a eureka moment – he was able to hearken back to his experience facing and addressing the same problem. While he mentioned that smoking was able to clear his mind, it also implied that smoking improved his episodic memory, which refers to the “conscious recollection of a personal experience that contains information on what has happened and also where and when it happened” (Pause *et al.*, 2013, p. 1). For Caloy, he felt “lighter” when he smoked, especially when he was struggling to think about something at work. As such, another similar story to Dionicio was shared by Caloy, who regularly labored in a rice storage house wherein he was assigned in lifting and filing the sacks of rice. He said that filing should be done precisely so that the space can be maximized. On an occasion, he faced trouble in arranging the sacks of rice. He mentioned that he took a rest and smoked so that he can “plan” well. After smoking, Caloy described the effects of smoking on his thought below. In Caloy’s case, it can be observed that smoking improved his concentration, which was manifested in how he was able to collect his ideas and apply them to his problem at work.

“Naa toy time nga di nako sila [mga sinako nga humay] gaka-arrange. Galisod gyod ko’g buhat ato. Nipahulay ko. Nanigarilyo sad dayon aron makaplano ko’g tarong. Didto na dayon nagawas-awas akong mga ideas. Human ato, akong gikolekta akong mga nahunahunaan unya mao tong na-pile nako’g sakto ang mga sako sa humay. Kanang iyang gitahi bitaw akong hunahuna.” (Caloy)

[“There was a time when I couldn’t arrange them (the sacks of rice) properly. I was having a hard time doing it. I rested for a while. I also smoked

so I can plan well. It was when all the ideas overflowed. And after that, I collected all my ideas, applied them and then successfully piled all the sacks of rice. It weaved my thought.”]

Ben remembered another event wherein smoking ignited his mind. He shared that when he just moved into the sitio, he barely knew other people aside from his wife’s uncle. Additionally, he had no idea how to do farm work. Hence, this unabled him to land a job to feed his family. He recalled that there came a point when they could scarcely eat in a day. Unfortunately, Ben could no longer afford to ask for the support of his wife’s uncle because ever since they arrived in the sitio, he had been helping Ben’s family financially, even giving them rice. After staying for two months, there was a moment when a clever idea came into his mind. He continued his story below:

“... ato nga mga panahon, bisag asa ra gapaingon akong hunahuna unya akong gipangbungkag ang akong mga gamit, akong bolsa sa akong karsones, ug bag para mangita og sensilyo para palit sa sigarilyo. Human nako’g panigarilyo, nakarelaks ko, unya natarong akong panghunahuna, unya ako dayong gikatulgan tanan. Mao tong human sa duha ka bulan nga pagpuyo namo diri, naa toy time nga nakahunahuna ko’g idea samtang gapanigarilyo ko. Akong giignan akong kaugalingon nga ‘nganong di ko magduol sa mga tao diri unya magtuon unsaon pagtrabaho sa uma?’ Mao tong nagtesting ko’g duol sa wa nako nailhi pero gakaulaw ko. Mao tong nanigarilyo ko una ayha ko niestorya sa ila unya baklay dayon ko’g hinay-hinay, dayon ako na dayon silang gipangutana kung pwede ba ko nila matagaa’g trabaho. Usahay pod akong tagaan og sigarilyo tong mga tao nga kabalo ko gapanigarilyo. Mao dayon tong

nabarkada nako sila unya ila na dayon kong giapil sa ilang sunod nga pag-labor.” (Ben)

[“...during those times, my thoughts were everywhere and so I rummaged all my things, my jeans’ pockets, and bags to look for coins to buy cigarettes. After I smoked, I felt relaxed and my thoughts were realigned, and then slept over them and everything that bothered me. And so after two months of staying here, there was a time when I was puffing my cigarettes and got an ingenious idea. I asked myself ‘why not I approach people and learn how to do farm work here?’ So I tried to approach a lot of new people but I was shy. So what I did before I talked to them was to light cigarettes, and then slowly walked towards them asked them and if they could give me a job. Sometimes, I offered cigarettes to those, I knew, who smoke. So there, we then became friends and they included me in their next schedule of farm labor.”]

In Ben’s narrative, it can be seen that smoking was also able to enhance his state of mind. It rewired his untangled thoughts that stemmed from his problem – unemployment that resulted in food insufficiency. His frustrations and overthinking about his family’s situation and the fact that he could not provide for their needs because of his inexperience in farm work were properly addressed through smoking. It can also be said that during those times, smoking became their family’s savior. Smoking gave him an idea of how to redeem his family from potential starvation. It also served a medium to extend his social network wherein he could potentially solve his problem. He was able to use smoking to meet people and enter into their world, wherein he could learn how to live in the sitio by doing farm labor. In general, the majority of the farmworkers gave accounts about how they were able to utilize smoking

to survive in life. Smoking helped them in situations wherein their cognitive abilities were tested to improve their performance at work and pull through those instances wherein their family's lives were at stake. The accounts of the farmworkers about smoking as a thought provoker and organizer may be attributed to the cognitive-enhancing effects of nicotine as forwarded by Valentine & Sofuoglu (2018) and Alhowail (2021). Farmworkers expressed that smoking can bolster their memory which is in line with the results of the study of Jubelt *et al.* (2008), who found that nicotine can enhance rapid and accurate episodic memory. Nicotine's benefits on brain performance have also been proven by Heishman *et al.* (2010), who discovered significant positive effects on six domains, namely fine motor, alerting attention-accuracy, orienting attention, short-term episodic memory accuracy, and working memory. These explicate the farmworkers' experiences wherein smoking was found beneficial for their thought process.

A Culture among Friends

Five farmworkers frequently smoked with their smoker friends. This was highlighted by Eduardo when asked about the situations when he would usually smoke: "*kanang magkita ko's akong mga amigo nga mga chain-smokers. Mag-estorya mi parte sa trabaho, pamilya, ug among panginabuhian. Samtang gaestorya mi, gapanigarilyo sad mi.*" ["*when I meet my friends who are also chain-smokers. We'd talk about work, family, and livelihood. While we're talking, we're also smoking.*"] This signified that cigarette was part of their social life. It was like food that is inseparable from any social gathering. They needed to smoke to maintain social connections, and, when necessary, share cigarettes to reinforce social networks. Anton illustrated that when smoking, "*mas samot gyod [kalingaw] og naa kay kauban nga makaestorya-*

estorya nga gapanigarilyo pod. Mao na dayon nang higayon nga grabe imong panigarilyo.” [“(it’s) even more (enjoyable) when you have a companion to talk to who’s also a smoker. That’s the time that you smoked endlessly.”] While joyfulness was cited as a reason, one apparent motive was that they also wanted to follow and keep up with their friends’ social norms in order to build and sustain social connections. This claim was evident in Ben’s response after having been asked about which part of their social interactions or gatherings did smoking usually come into play. He answered:

“Sa among tapok-tapok, boring kaayo akong paminaw kung di mi tanan manigarilyo. Kung naa koy makita nga barkada nga manigarilyo, mosunod nasad dayon ang usa unya tanan na dayon. Kanang makita nako sila nga lingaw kaayo nga gaestorya-estorya og bisan unsa pareha anang kung aha nasad magtapok, gakaengganyo sad ko manigarilyo. Dapat ko manigarilyo aron kanang makasabay bitaw sa ila.” (Ben)

[“In our gatherings, I felt like it’s very boring if not all of us smoke. Whenever I see a friend lights a cigarette, another friend then follows and everyone else. As I see them enjoying it while talking about things like where to bond next, I’m also enticed to smoke. I have to smoke so that I can keep up with them.”]

As can be deduced from his response, Ben’s peers were influential in his smoking behavior. Within their peer group, Ben regarded smoking as necessary for creating and maintaining social connections, which were requisites to experience joy and promote a vibrant atmosphere during gatherings. In turn, a sense of belongingness or “*pakikisama*” (a Filipino trait, which means willing to go with the group) can be experienced by all group members. Ben’s story also showed how the

observance of social norms and one's mere presence in the group affected smoking behavior. Hence, this posed social pressure on the part of Ben as he needed to "keep up" with his friends as a way of his involvement in the group. To maintain their bonds, the farmworkers also assured that they shared cigarettes with each other, especially when any of the members could not buy one because of a tight budget. This meant that the farmworkers acknowledged their shared responsibility as members of their community – that is, to help each other in times of need, which can be termed "damayan" – another Filipino trait. This mutual accountability among group members was a key to maintaining their group dynamics, which was done by sharing cigarettes. The following passages elucidated the concept of cigarette sharing among the farmworkers and their friends.

"Naa sad koy mga barkada nga pirmi gahatag og sigarilyo. Kung way ako, pirmi ko makapangayo sa ila. Bisan pa lagi'g ni mahal na ang sigarilyo, inana ra gyapon sila. Pirmi sila manghatag." (Caloy)

["I also have friends who always share their cigarettes. If I don't have one, I can always ask from them. Even if the price of cigarettes is already high, they're still the same. They always give."]

"Kanang magtapok mi, kung ang akong mga barkada way sigarilyo, pirminte gyod mi gahinataga tapos manigarilyo dayon. Usahay gani maglikit mi anang dahon sa lumboy kay mahal na lagi ang sigarilyo. Mao na ang kibale sumpay sa among bisyo." (Eduardo)

["When we gather, if my friends don't have cigarette, we always share and then smoke together. We sometimes use duhat leaves because cigarettes are pricey. That's the extension of our vices."]

In Eduardo's response, the unavailability of cigarettes due to their high price was not a problem since all of them could always find other alternatives to attend to their vices. Similar to this was Caloy's story of an incident wherein their urge to smoke made them think of a clever idea to obtain cigarettes.

"Naa gani to'y higayon atong 2010, katong kami's akong mga barkada, mga ulitawo pami ato, nakahunahuna mi'g maayo nga idea aron makapanigarilyo mi. Paingon mi ato nga time sa duol nga suba kay manikop og isda ug magbonding. Kanang suba ang among pirmi tambayan. Samtang padulong mi didto, ayha pami kabantay nga wa man diay mi sigarilyo, unya wa sad mi kwarta pangpalit. Nakadesisyon dayon mi nga mangutang sa tindahan unya bayran ra dayon namo'g makasweldo nami's among panginadlawan. Kay ako raman lagi ang murag suod atong tag-iya's tindahan, akoy nangutang. Mao tong giputang sad ko's tag-iya. Sa suba, kung manikop mi, pirminte mi gapanigarilyo kay tugnaw. Samtang gasugba-sugba mi's among kuha, manigarilyo sad mi. Kung magestoryahanay mi, samot nanang mga binutbot, grabe among sigarilyo ana unya lanog-lanog among katawa. Tsada gyod makig-estorya sa among magbarkada kung manigarilyo. Daghan kaayo mi'g maestoryahan." (Caloy)

["There was even an instance in 2010, when my friends and I, who were still teenagers, got some wise ideas on how to secure some cigarettes. That time, we're heading to the nearby river to catch some fish and bond. The river was our usual place to hang out. While we're on our way going there, we realized that we didn't have some cigarettes and we didn't have money to buy one. We then decided to ask for cigarettes from the sari-sari store and pay them

later by the time we had money from farm work. Since I was the only one in the group who was quite close to the sari-sari store owner, I did the honor to ask him. So the owner gave me some. In the river, while we're catching fish, we also always smoked since it was cold. While we're sitting and grilling our catch, we smoked as well. When we're talking about anything, especially nonsense, we intensely smoked with a resounding laugh. It was always nice to talk with my friends while smoking. We can talk about a lot of things.”]

From Caloy's story, it can be realized that they viewed smoking as an inseparable component of any social occasion. Hence, they looked for ingenious ways to obtain cigarettes so that they could have something to consume during social activities and interactions – catching fish and grilling their catch. He also highlighted that they experienced joy in conversing with their friends while smoking. A similar instance was shared by Gibo, who said, *“gapanigarilyo ko kung uban nako akong mga barkada diha's among tapokanan, kung aha mi gabaraha. Sige mi'g estorya og bisan unsa. Bisan pa gani'g wa pami nagsugod og estorya, busy na'g aso-aso among baba ana. Tsada kaayo among paminaw.”* [“I smoke when I'm with my friends there in our gathering area, where we play cards. We talk limitlessly about anything nonsense. Even if the conversation has not yet started, our mouths are busy puffing cigarettes. We feel good.”] Gibo mentioned about the role of cigarette as a conversation lubricant and this was almost observed in the abovementioned accounts of other farmworkers. As a conversation lubricant, smoking enabled the farmworkers and their respective friends to have a productive or smooth flow of conversation. This consequently gave them a “pleasant” feeling – perhaps, this feeling can be linked to the accomplishment of being able to talk about a lot of topics. This was evident in the story of Anton when he was asked to cite an instance of smoking activity with his friends.

“Kintahay lugar, kanang nibisita ko’s basakan. Makita man nako na’g kalit akong mga barkada nga gabisita sad sa ilang uma. Di gyod na mahitabo nga di nako sila duolan. Sindi dayon ko’g sigarilyo ana unya mangutana dayon ko’s ila og ‘naa kay sigarilyo diha?’ Muingon mana sila’g ‘oo, naa,’ so tanan na dayon mi manigarilyo. Mag-estoryahanay na dayon mi ana’g unsa among mga namatikdan sa among uma ug mga bisan unsa ra. Di gyod ko makaadto’g basakan nga way isa ka kaha nga sigarilyo sa akong bolsa unya naa man sad nay mga higayon nga wa nay mga sigarilyo akong mga barkada kay way budget, maong ako gyod na silang tagaan, ignon nako sila’g ‘o, diay sigarilyo, manigarilyo ta.’ Hinay ra lagi na’ng isa paingon duha ka oras para ana, unya minimum ra na ang tulo ka stick nga among mahurot. Ana nga mga oras, padayon among estorya ana. Kung di namo mabatian ang init sa adlaw sa among luyo, di mi manguli hangtod sa naay moingon isa sa amoa nga ‘hoy, murag tingpaniudto na galing. Gutom na galing.” (Anton)

[“For example, when I make rounds on the rice field. I accidentally saw my friends from afar who were visiting their farm as well. Of course, I couldn’t avoid not to approach them. I then lit my cigarette and asked them ‘do you have cigarettes there?’ They said ‘yes, I have,’ so all of us started smoking. We then talked about what we have noticed on our farm and just anything. I can’t go to the rice field without a pack of cigarettes and there were times that my friends had no cigarettes due to no budget so I always shared by saying ‘here’s a stick, let’s smoke.’ 1 to 2 hours were too short for that and then 3 sticks were just the minimum number we could consume. In that span of time, the conversation continued. If we can’t feel the heat of the sun on our back, we don’t go home

until such time that one of us will say ‘hey, I think it’s already lunchtime. I’m starving.’]

Anton recognized the importance of cigarettes in any conversation. Hence, cigarette was his conversation-starter pack. This was exhibited when he made sure that before their interaction, everyone had cigarettes. It was for this reason that he always brought cigarettes with him when he visited the rice farm. Anton also recognized the power of smoking to lengthen time, which can be translated into conversation productivity. Generally, all farmworkers’ accounts above suggested that smoking was part of their culture. As a culture, this was enlivened by the presence of cigarettes in any of their social congregation which created a bond and improved social interactions. Smoking as a culture was also evidenced by observing group social norms (i.e., smoking), sharing cigarettes, and looking for different ways to obtain cigarettes and their substitutes that were key to building, maintaining, and solidifying social connections and networks.

The result of the present work extended what was found in other existing pieces of literature, highlighting smoking as a vehicle for socialization to strengthen and make group bonds. Mohammadnezhad & Kengganpanich (2021) uncovered that for adult smokers in Fiji, smoking had the capacity to establish a friendship. One of the informants of Onen & Watson (2021) highlighted that smoking can form a bond among smokers. Miething *et al.* (2016) asserted that smokers usually socialize with other smokers and they tend to deselect non-smokers from their networks. According to Kueh *et al.* (2021), social bond (attachment, involvement, commitment, and belief) was strongly associated with smoking behavior.

An Integral Part of Life

When asked about their daily routines and which of their parts wherein smoking entered the scene, five farmworkers responded that smoking was omnipresent in their lives and was connected to their day-to-day activities. Farmworkers underscored that they smoked the moment they woke up, after or while drinking coffee, and after eating breakfast. Caloy said, “*kanang momata ko, gapangitaon siya sa akong lawas. Kanang murag, kung magmata ko, ang una nga mosulod sa akong hunahuna kay ‘lamia manigarilyo oy.’ Kay kuan ba, adik, adik na gyod. Pirminte na gyod nako siya mahunahunaan.*” [“*the moment I wake up, my body always looks for it. It’s like, when I wake up, that’s the first thing that comes into my mind, saying ‘I like to smoke.’ Because of addiction... I’m addicted already. I always think of it.*”] Caloy reasoned that he smoked because his mind yearned for it. For him, this yearning was interpreted as an “addiction,” which was displayed by his intense craving so much so that the thought of smoking frequently echoed on his mind. Perhaps, this phenomenon that he termed himself as an “addiction” can be ascribed to the effects of nicotine, which gave him a pleasant feeling. Sharing a similar account with Caloy was Felimon, who mentioned, “*sa dihang momata ko, magkuha ko ana’g duha ka stick sa sigarilyo. Ayha ko magluto og pagkaon ug mamahaw, makahurot sad ko ana’g duha ka sticks. Ako nang gihimo ang sigarilyo og kauban ug kalingawan diri’s uma.*” [“*when I wake up, I get 2 sticks of cigarettes. Before I cook food and eat my breakfast, I can also consume another 2 sticks. I make cigarette as my companion and pastime here on the farm.*”] It should be noted that Felimon was the only single among the rest of the participants. This could explain why he regarded cigarettes as his comrades and part of his pastime in his everyday routine, particularly in working alone on the farm. Perhaps, for Felimon, every time he smoked, he was being hit with nostalgic events, wherein he reminisced

all the happy memories he had with friends while smoking. Thus, it can also be understood that in Felimon's case, loneliness could be linked to smoking. He might be longing for a companion that is why he used cigarettes in place of the former. Meanwhile, Gibo underscored the following statement: "*gapanigarilyo ko kada buntag. Usahay, ayha mangape ug mokaon. Pirmi gyod ko gasigarilyo. Ambot lang... Murag naanad na ko. Tsada kaayo akong paminaw kung makapanigarilyo ko. Di gyod makompleto akong adlaw kung wala na.*" ["*I smoke every morning. Sometimes, before coffee and eating. I always smoke. I don't know... I got used to it. I feel so good every time I smoke. My day wouldn't be complete without it.*"] Gibo emphasized that his body got used to it, which was similar to Caloy's case. In line with this, nicotine dependence, manifested through Gibo's receptivity to smoking, may also be responsible for this. This was evidenced when he mentioned that smoking made him feel good. As a consequence, smoking then became an inseparable element of his life, saying that smoking completed his day. Smoking dependence was also ascribed by Eduardo to his tendency to smoke every after coffee by saying, "*ganahan gyod ko manigarilyo kay paminaw nako murag gatulo akong laway kung di ko kasigarilyo.*" ["*I really like to smoke because I felt like I salivate if I can't smoke.*"] For Eduardo, salivation was perceived as a sign of craving for cigarettes. Another similar instance of smoking for a different reason was shared by Ben, who said, "*kung momata ko, inom kape, ug mamahaw, manigarilyo dayon ko ana aron pampawala sa luod.*" ["*when I wake up, drink coffee, and eat breakfast, I then smoke after to remove the disgusting after-taste.*"] This meant that Ben turned to smoke to remove his perceived disagreeable after-taste of the food he ate. This further implied that he used it as his mitigating tool to address his food dissatisfaction or food disgust. Anton mentioned the following statement when asked about why he smoked:

“Tsada siya sa pamati. Murag imo na siyang na-habit ba, imong bisyo. Kung mamahog ko’g manok, manigarilyo ko. Taas na lagi kaayo na’ng dyis minutos nga interval gikan anang pagsugod nimo’g isa ka stick hangtod sa mahuman ka ana. Imo na gyod siyang nabatasan nga pirmi nimo gabuhaton matag karon ug unya. Kintahay lugar inani, naglingkod ta, paminaw nimo ana murag naa gyoy kulang, unya imong sigarilyo naa diha’s lamesa, so magkuha ka’g isa, unya sindihan nimo samtang gaestorya-estorya. Naa lagi time nga kung ganahan ka’g panigarilyo, di na ka ganaha’g undang. Katong wa pa ko naminyo, bisan pa’g unsa akong trabahoon, kung makahigayon ko’g sigarilyo, manigarilyo gyod ko. Samtang busy akong kamot og trabaho, ako pong baba ana sige’g buga’g aso. Kibale nahimo na gyod nako siya’ng partner sa akong kinabuhi.” (Anton)

[“It feels nice. It’s like your habit, your vice. When I feed the chickens, I smoke. A 10-minute interval between starting and finishing a stick is too long. You made it part of your behavior that you do every now and then. For example, we’re seated like this. While you’re seating, you feel like there’s something missing, and then your cigarettes are on the table, so you get another one, and light it while talking. There will always be a time when you want to smoke, you don’t want to end it. When I was still single before, whatever type of work I was in when I got the chance to smoke, I always smoked. While my hand was busy working, my mouth was also puffing cigarettes. In a way, I made it my partner in life.”]

In Anton’s statement, it can be understood that smoking was also part of his daily routine. For him, smoking was a form of habit and behavior – grounded on

cigarette's pleasurable effects – which were displayed through smoking repetition and smoking intensity. He cited that the mere presence of a cigarette that was within his reach compelled him to smoke as it contained his feeling of emptiness or longing for something to the extent that he did not want to end it. Hence, two factors affecting his understanding of smoking as a habit were the availability or accessibility of cigarettes and another one was, again, the pleasure feeling that smoking gave him, such as in the cases of Caloy and Gibo.

Three farmworkers were somehow aware that smoking had baneful effects on their health, income, and relationship. Ben said, *“ingon gani’ng uban nga mas di pa delikado ang moinom kaysa manigarilyo kay kanang sigarilyo naa nay gibana-bana nga 100 ka kemikal. Mao nang makadaot siya’s atong lawas ug makaadik.”* [“others even say that it’s safer to drink liquor than to smoke cigarettes because a cigarette contains approximately 100 chemicals. That’s why it can be harmful to our bodies and cause addiction.”] Felimon stated, *“para sa ako, makadaot ning akong pagpanigarilyo sa akong panglawas.”* [“for me, I have a feeling that my smoking habit can have negative effect on my health.”] Because of these perceived risks of smoking, farmworkers were also scared that they will experience them later in their lives. Ben and Felimon expressed that quitting smoking could save up their money especially now that the price of cigarettes is high. Ben also recognized the possibility of getting hospitalized because of smoking and this thought scared him because of their socioeconomic status; they could not afford hospitalization. His fear and financial situation made him feel that he should stop smoking. Caloy also shared that the disapproval of loved ones, just like his ex-girlfriend, towards his smoking behavior was the major cause of their fight. Thus, smoking can bring peril to relationship. Although they recognized the pernicious effects of smoking on their health, income, and

relationship, all these negative perceptions they had about smoking were outweighed by the pleasure that the nicotine gave them along with their positive meanings of smoking. Hence, their decision to continue or stop smoking was fraught with immense confusion. Ben recalled a story, wherein he experienced the effects of smoking on his health.

“Naa toy isa ka buntag nga nimata ko human sa isa ka adlaw nga grabe nakong sigarilyo, grabe ka sakit akong tutunlan. Sakit gyod siya. Unya akong buhok kanang murag gapang-inaton ba, unya gisakitan dayon ko ato’g ulo nga murag gakatay sa akong liog. Dayon nanigarilyo sad ko, ug niinom og tambal. Nawala ang sakit sa akong tutunlan ug ulo. Sunod adlaw, nahitabo nasad to. Sakit nasad akong tutunlan ug ulo. Nanigarilyo nasad dayon ko aron mawala ang kasakit. Mao nang kada mahitabo na’s akoo, manigarilyo ko. Paminaw nako, ang sigarilyo ang tambal sa ila.” (Ben)

[“There was one morning when I woke up after intense smoking the day before, I felt something very irritating in my throat. It was really sore. And then my hair is like being pulled and got a headache that went down to my neck. Then, I smoked again and took medicine. The sore throat and headache were gone. The next day, the same thing happened in the morning. My throat and head hurt. I then smoked for the pain to go away. So every time that happens to me, I always smoke. I feel like cigarettes have become their treatment.”]

In Ben’s story, it can be concluded that smoking was a vicious cycle – he smoked and when experienced the unpleasant effects of smoking, he also used cigarettes as their antidote. Ergo, it goes to show that smoking then turned into a repetitive activity, something that he cannot escape from. When asked about his

thoughts about the said experience, he highlighted that the repetition was an “addiction.” This was also in accord with the other farmworkers who stated that they could not let go of smoking because their body always craved it. Gibo shared that he tried to stop smoking, but it only took him three days and after that, he went back to it because his mind was always reminded that he should smoke. If he completely stopped smoking, he further added, “*maapektohan akong baga kay basin ang nicotine nalang ang gapugong ani. Kay pirmi ko kapoyon kung way sigarilyo.*” [“*my lungs will be affected because maybe the nicotine is the only thing that holds it. Because I feel tired if there’s no cigarette.*”] Similar to Gibo, Felimon said, “*murag naa na dayon kulang*” [“*something would then be missing*”] if he stops smoking because of dependence – his body had gotten used to it. Farmworkers’ responses had provided another evidence of how smoking can lead to “addiction,” which is defined as the “strong, usually passionate liking for something” (Baumeister, 2017, p. 68). Consequently, this situated the farmworkers in a place where they lost their free will – that is, smoking was the only choice they had to satisfy their strong desire of wanting cigarettes although they held some notions about the possible repercussion of smoking on their well-being. In general, heavy smokers like the farmworkers were faced with great challenges to stop smoking as they were physically, emotionally, and socially dependent on cigarettes. Farmworkers’ accounts contradicted the results stating that higher knowledge about the health risk of cigarette smoking leads to a high likelihood to stop smoking (Dawood *et al.*, 2016). However, it agreed with Dîrțu & Soponaru (2014), who highlighted that smokers are well aware of the harmful effects, particularly about addiction, but are unwilling to modify their behavior.

While other farmworkers welcomed the claims that smoking can be nocuous to health, Eduardo’s case gave an opposing notion. He uttered about the absence of the

negative effects of smoking up to the present time on his parent's health, who did not inform him about the possible consequence of smoking on health when he was younger and who rather accentuated the benefits of smoking, which was its capacity to act as an insect repellent. In fact, in the preceding section, it was his parents to whom he imputed his smoking initiation. Using the current healthy situation of his parents as a point of reference had led him to challenge the previous conception that smoking has detrimental effects on the body. Resultantly, this belief made him think that smoking was not absolutely bad.

“Sa karon, gapadayon pa gyapon ko’g sigarilyo kay naandan na man nako. Nakuha nako siya sa akong mga ginikanan. 83 years old na akong mga ginikanan unya wa pa gyod nako sila nakit-an nga nagsakit tungod ana. Moingon man ganing uban nga makadaot daw sa atong lawas ang pagpanigarilyo, pero lahi man ang kaso sa akong ginikanan. So okay ra gyod manigarilyo.” (Eduardo)

[“As of now, I still continue smoking because I’m used to it. I got it from my parents. My parents are already 83 years old, and I have not seen them getting sick because of cigarettes. Others would even say that smoking can be bad for our health, but my parents’ case is different. So smoking is really okay.”]

Overall, it can be acknowledged that for the farmworkers, smoking became part of their daily lives, especially during the morning because of addiction, loneliness, dependence, habit, pleasure, motivation, companionship, and relief that smoking gave them. Farmworkers had different thoughts about the damaging effects of smoking. Not only was smoking inimical to health but also to socioeconomic status and relationships. However, they could not let go of smoking because it became an

inseparable component of their lives. They also feared that the disappearance of these positive effects might cause the collapse of their bodies. For these reasons along with the absence of noticeable evidence that smoking can really jeopardize the health, the farmworkers continued smoking.

Proposed Conceptual Framework of Smoking as a Communication Social Practice

In the preceding section, it was inferred that there were multiple factors, reasons and situations that came out from their narratives and responses relative to the farmworkers' experience with smoking. Based on these unearthed factors, reasons and situations, constituting the themes that represented the meaning of smoking among the farmworkers, a framework is proposed (Figure 2). The framework shows the relationship between the factors of smoking (sociocultural, psychological, and knowledge and awareness), and smoking constructs (smoking initiation, tendency, and cessation).

Based on the framework, it was hypothesized that sociocultural factors, namely parental and peer smoking were related to the farmworkers' smoking initiation and tendency. If their parents and friends had not been smokers, the farmworkers would have not become smokers as well. Farmworkers' exposure to smoker parents and peers led them to begin smoking and eventually affected their smoking tendency. Correspondingly, they were also major determinants that prevented them to stop smoking. Farmworkers received direct (giving sticks of cigarettes) and indirect (no disapproval) support from their parent smokers. Also, for the farmworkers, smoking, as an inseparable element during social congregations, was considered a "culture"

among friends wherein cigarette sharing and observance of smoking norms were followed. In this vein, it was hypothesized that farmworkers' social congregation with friends affected smoking tendency. Different psychological problems, triggering the farmworkers to smoke in order to endure them, also emerged from the analysis; hence, it was theorized that psychological factors, namely stress, tiredness, anxiousness, confusion, anger, hate, loneliness, boredom, pleasure, addiction, habit, hunger, and food disgust were positively associated with smoking tendency and negatively correlated to smoking cessation. When the farmworkers experienced psychological problems, their tendency to smoke increased. Regardless of the knowledge and awareness levels, it was highlighted that the farmworkers initiated and tended to smoke. This was so because as mentioned in the preceding section, the majority of the farmworkers demonstrated to have knowledge and awareness about the adverse consequence of smoking on their health, income, and relationship. Thus, it was hypothesized that farmworkers whether with low, moderate, or high levels of knowledge and awareness of the baneful effects of smoking on the mentioned aspects of life were positively correlated to smoking initiation and tendency and were not correlated to smoking cessation. Most of them could not let go of smoking because of the sociocultural and psychological factors indicated in the framework.

Generally, it was conjectured that on one hand, sociocultural factors and knowledge and awareness (again, regardless of the levels) resulted in smoking initiation, leading to smoking tendency. On the other hand, sociocultural and psychological, and knowledge and awareness were all major hurdles towards smoking cessation that in turn, engendered smoking tendency. Ultimately, smoking tendency led to smoking continuation. Overall, the framework attempts to shed light on the connections among the factors affecting the farmworkers' conceptualization of

smoking, which consequently defined their actions – smoking initiation, smoking tendency, and resisting smoking cessation that all resulted in smoking continuation or maintenance, thereby making smoking as a cultural norm.

Figure 2. Determinants of smoking as a communication social practice

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

Multiple reports and studies have shown that smoking is associated with various diseases, including heart disease, stroke, and lung cancer, among many others. In particular, low-and-middle-income countries like the Philippines are not spared by this health epidemic. In the study by Yamaguchi *et al.* (2021), it was found that cigarette smoking is prevalent among Filipino men in a highly urbanized area. Similarly, Punzalan *et al.* (2013) discovered in their national survey that the smoking burden was observed highest among male rural dwellers. This is consistent with the situation in a rural area called Sitio Lalawan in Malaybalay, Bukidnon, wherein smoking is commonly observed among male farmworkers. A lot of studies have been conducted quantitatively about this matter not just in the Philippines but across the globe. However, the availability of qualitative studies is relatively scant. As of this writing, there has been no study yet that investigates qualitatively the experiences, motivations, and factors affecting smoking behavior among the said population in the Philippines, particularly in Bukidnon. Exploring the smoking phenomenon through qualitative means will give us a better understanding, and a more nuanced and detailed information about it, which are beneficial for smoking cessation efforts. To this end, this study was conducted to explore the meanings of smoking among the current farmworker smokers in Sitio Lalawan through the lens of sociocultural communication tradition. Specifically, the study explored their ways of defining smoking, the articulations of their smoking experience, and how their meanings and concepts of smoking drive them to smoke.

Narrative inquiry was deemed to be the appropriate qualitative approach as it aims to reveal people's meaning of their experiences. Through individual open interviews that lasted from 18 to 45 minutes, the stories were collected from seven participants, who agreed to take part in the study. The interview was then transcribed and the data was processed through restorying followed by narrative thematic analysis.

The results showed that the farmworkers held meanings that agreed and contrasted with the findings of the previous studies. The narrative thematic analysis showed five themes, constituting the meaning of smoking, which were a parent and peer's influence, a means to manage negative feelings and emotions, a thought provoker and organizer, a culture among friends, and an integral part of life.

Farmworkers believed that they inherited smoking from their parents and were influenced by friends, who were smokers. They modeled their smoking behavior from their parents, who did not condone them when they were caught smoking at a young age. Older peers' verbal and non-verbal cues were also found impactful to their smoking initiation. Some of the farmworkers were caught in predicaments, which made them turn to smoking to relieve their negative feelings and emotions, specifically stress. They also recalled some previous occasions wherein lighting and puffing cigarettes facilitated them to plan well at work. Smoking was regarded by the farmworkers as part of their culture, which had been used during social congregation, wherein observance of the smoking norms like smoking while talking, cigarette sharing, and finding alternatives for cigarettes were demonstrated. Farmworkers emphasized that smoking was an inseparable part of their lives because of multiple reasons such as habit, dependence, and companionship among many others. While

most of them recognized the effects of smoking on health, they still continued to smoke because of “addiction,” which was characterized in different ways like intense craving. All these perceptions they had about smoking were also factors affecting smoking initiation and continuation.

Conclusions

Based on the proposed framework (Figure 2), highlighting that smoking is a communication social practice, it can be concluded that it would be difficult for the farmworkers to stop their smoking habit. Smoking is their life and breaking it would be tantamount to unweaving the social fabric that binds the members of the farming community. Smoking connects their social, emotional, cultural, and economic life because through smoking, they can communicate what they want to convey. As an accepted gesture, transactions are made easier and interactions safer because smoking can serve as a thinking and deciding platform given the factors that shape people’s lives. It can be surmised that, perhaps, it is the parents who need to be educated rather than the children. The older generation should set the example in cognizance of their roles as models worth emulating as the development of young people’s perceived norms are influenced by the verbal and non-verbal (smoking gestures) messages they received from adults. The adage “*ang maling ginagawa ng matanda ay nagiging tama sa mata ng bata*” [“the wrongdoing of adult becomes right through the eyes of a child”] indeed supports the finding that smoking is a communication social practice that may be hard to change if norms cannot be transformed. Also, smoking is farmworkers’ cultural norm, wherein pro-smoking attitudes and atmosphere are promoted, thereby driving them to continue smoking. In other words, smoking characterizes what they should do without regard for the

eventual noxious effect of smoking on health. Smoking dictates their etiquette and the meaning of normal and acceptable behavior in given contexts. As members of their smoking community, they are expected to perform the prescribed norms. Moreover, smoking is their main way to bounce back from the lowest and hardest point of their lives. They find refuge in smoking, which enables them to temporarily escape from reality in order to survive. Therefore, facing everyday's struggles as breadwinners of the family would be even harder if they stop smoking. Furthermore, it can be inferred that smoking has constructed an identity that personifies their sense of self. Gender is a link that intertwines smoking and culture, wherein smoking is seen as a 'manly' activity, socially acceptable, and normative behavior among men; hence, these rationalize why smoking is prevalent among males such as the participants of this study. All these arguments corroborate the present study's main notion that smoking is a communication social practice, which is habitually performed by a group of people, who gradually influence more and more other individuals to engage in the same practice if no intervention is employed.

Recommendations

The present findings provided implications for both practice and future research. For successful smoking cessation, it is imperative to understand the concepts that smokers have about smoking, thereby influencing and increasing their motivation to engage in such an activity. Hence, the present study was conducted.

Practical Recommendations

- In this study, it was found that parental smoking was highly influential for the farmworkers to start and maintain to smoke. Most of the farmworkers, who are

now fathers, might also influence their children to do the same, thereby making cigarettes an inseparable part of their children's lives, which then makes the smoking epidemic a vicious cycle. Most of them showed knowledge and awareness about the harmful effects of smoking but were still adamant to stop as smoking had become an integral component of their lives. Hence, there is a need to craft and implement smoking cessation program and campaigns that are tailored for them. To this end, it is recommended that public health professionals, Malaybalay City Health Office, and the DOH do counseling on smoking cessation among the farmworkers that highlight the adverse effects of smoking on the health of their family or loved ones, who are exposed to secondhand and third-hand smoke (the smoke that remains on the surface). In this study, family modeling was one of the main reasons for the farmworkers to smoke. Thus, if the farmworkers are successfully counseled to quit smoking, their children will be less likely to start smoking and eventually develop a dependence on it.

- The same as the case of the parent smokers, friends were also key to influencing smoking initiation and maintenance among the farmworkers. In this regard, their friends became their triggers to smoke, especially during social congregations, wherein cigarette sharing and observing social norms were requisites to maintaining social connections. Provided that counseling the farmworkers successfully made them decide to quit cigarettes, the farmworkers should talk about their decision to their smoker friends so that they will not smoke during social gatherings. Farmworkers may also opt not to go with their smoker friends but with their non-smoker friends.

- In this study, smoking helped the farmworkers manage unpleasant feelings and emotions, such as stress, anxiousness, tiredness, and loneliness among many others. For this reason, public health professionals and health institutions must also give some healthier and more effective alternatives to address these negative feelings and emotions. These may include exercising, meditating, relaxation strategies, or simple breathing exercises.
- Smoking was also considered by the farmworkers as an inseparable component of their lives – they smoked the moment they woke up, before, during, and after coffee, after a meal, or any part of their daily routine. Hence, farmworkers may consider breaking this pattern by replacing cigarettes with something else like drinking a glass of water when waking up and as a replacement for coffee so as not to trigger them to light up cigarettes. After a meal, maybe farmworkers can wait 15 minutes for the craving to pass or do other things that might help them forget that they need to smoke.

Development Communication

- For development communication (devcom) professionals, they should consider using the results of this study as a springboard for producing culturally tailored educational campaign materials and by collaborating with the concerned agency such as the DOH for scientific validity. For example, the visual component and narrative attribute of comics translate scientific concepts more concrete through the comic's capacity to represent and portray structures and phenomena, falling outside human sensory experiences in an entertaining way (Alemany-Pagès *et al.*, 2022). As such, comic has been found to be successful

in increasing awareness and knowledge acquisition resulting in the promotion of people's beliefs, attitudes, and behavior change (Jee & Anggoro, 2012). Hence, devcom professionals should consider developing a comic that highlights how family modeling and peer influence can influence smoking initiation and maintenance and the effects of smoking on the health of family members and friends who are non-smokers, and the impact of smoking on their income and relationships. It should also be assured that in the development of the comic, the context must be localized so that the farmworkers can relate to the story and message conveyed in the material.

- Audiovisual material has also been found to be effective in educating low-educated adolescents about smoking that induced negative attitudes toward smoking (de Graaf *et al.*, 2016), and increased motivation to quit smoking (Ismail *et al.*, 2021). Thus, communication specialists with the aid of public health professionals must also produce audiovisual materials about smoking and the steps on how to quit with respect to the smoking triggers that were highlighted in this study.
- Ultimately, community health seminars on smoking to be attended by the doctors to the barrios and community nurses from the DOH as resource persons can also be conducted among the farmworkers and/or their families in Sitio Lalawan. In the said seminar, the communication materials mentioned above can then be distributed and shown. After the campaign, communication professionals might also consider doing a follow-up investigation about the impact of the produced materials and the seminar on the knowledge,

awareness, and practice of the farmworkers in order to ascertain the campaign's effectiveness. This campaign is deemed to inform and raise awareness that is expected to aid the farmworkers in making informed decisions that are crucial to their personal and their family's wellbeing.

Policymaking

- It has already been five years since the approval and implementation of the smoke-free ordinance in the City of Malaybalay. The ordinance prohibits smoking in public places and the selling and distribution of cigarettes. However, smoking is still prevalent in other locations, especially in rural areas like Sitio Lalawan. Therefore, there is a need for the local government to revisit the enforcement of this ordinance as its implementation is only centered on the populations in the city proper. The implementation should also reach the rural areas by coordinating with the barangay and purok officials and the barangay health centers. Although there may be a smoking cessation program that is put in place by the City Health Office, it is also important to tailor the approach to the needs and context of the smokers. For example, for the farmworkers, using the results of this study as bases for personalizing the method in encouraging them to stop smoking would probably be prudent. More importantly, the cessation program and its facilities must also be accessible to the farmworkers as the City Health Office is relatively far from rural areas like Sitio Lalawan.

Further Research

- The present qualitative research was able to generate a conceptual framework shown in the preceding section, wherein hypotheses,

propositions, and assumptions were forwarded for future work. In the framework, as discussed in the results and discussion section, the relationships and associations of the sociocultural factors, psychological factors, and knowledge and awareness, can be considered independent variables, and the dependent variables are smoking initiation, smoking tendency, and smoking cessation. In this respect, it is advised that future researchers conduct a quantitative study to test the relationships of these variables among the farmworkers in the same or other areas in order to gain more understanding or generate knowledge on the smoking epidemic in the rural areas of Malaybalay City.

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ANNEXES

ANNEX A

PERMISSION LETTER

University of the Philippines Open University
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies
Los Baños, Laguna, 4031 Philippines

Marso 18, 2022

Hon. Edgar L. Hernando
Barangay Captain, Barangay Linabo
Malaybalay City, 8700 Bukidnon Philippines

Tinahod namo nga Kapitan:

Maayong adlaw!

Ako si Reymark Padla Malinda, lumulupyo sa Purok-4, Sitio Lalawan niining atong barangay. Ako kasamtangang ga iskswela sa University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU) ubos sa programa nga Master of Development Communication.

Ayha ko mugradwar, ako gikinahanglan nga muhimo ug musulat sa akong research o thesis, kung aha ang akong hilisgutan mao ang pagpanigariyo sa mga trabahador sa uma (farmworkers o laborers) nga kasamtangang nagpuyo sa Purok-4, Sitio Lalawan. Sa akong thesis, gusto nako mahibaw-an kung unsa para kanila ang pagpanigariyo pinaagi sa interbiyo nga mahitabo sa traynta minutos ngadto sa isa ka oras. Ang interbiyo ipahigayon diha sa gawas sa amoang panimalay o puluy-anan sa mga partisipante – depende sa ilang mauyonan – karung Marso 19, 20, 26, 27, ug Abril 9, 10, 2022. Aduna akoy gi bana-bana nga lima ka partisipante sa nasangpit nga interbiyo.

Ikaw makasalig nga ang mga partisipante dili madaot o masakitan sa bisan unsa o asa nga aspito. Ang ilang pag-apil boluntaryo lamang; busa, kung mudesisyon sila nga muapil sa una, pwede pa gihapon sila nga dili mupadayon kamulo ang interbiyo. Alang sa pagprotekta sa ilang pagkatawo ug impormasyon, ako ug akoang research adviser lamang ang makabalo sa ilang mga tinuod nga pangalan ug insakto nga puloy-anan. Dugang pa niini, amoang tumanon ang minimum public health standards nga gitakda sa Department of Health mahitungod sa COVID-19.

Niining bahina, ako magahangyo ug maglaum sa imong pagtugot nga mupahigayon sa maong kalihukan.

Daghang salamat ug ikaw panalanginan sa atong buhi nga Diyos.

Kanimo matinahuron,

Reymark Padla Malinda
Estudyante

Gitugutan:

Hon. Edgar L. Hernando

ANNEX B

CONSENT TO TAKE PART IN RESEARCH

TITLE OF STUDY

Exploring the Meaning of Smoking among Farmworkers in Sitio Lalawan, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon

PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR

Reymark P. Malinda

Student, Master of Development Communication
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies
University of the Philippines Open University
0905-8738-732
rpmalinda@up.edu.ph

PURPOSE OF STUDY

You are being asked to take part in this research. Before you decide to participate, it is important that you understand why this research is being done and what it will involve. Please read the following information carefully and ask the researcher if there is anything that is not clear or if you need more information.

The purpose of this study is to identify the meaning smoking among farmworkers in Sitio Lalawan, Linabo, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon. Your participation will largely contribute to the meaning-making research that might be an additional knowledge to the existing studies about smoking in the Philippines.

STUDY PROCEDURES

If you agree to take part in this study, the researcher will conduct an interview with you. You will be asked to share your experiences with smoking through storytelling via Zoom. If there is a need for elaboration and clarification, follow-up questions will also be asked. During the session, you are allowed to use your language of convenience.

The interview is projected to take up to 30 minutes to 1 hour to complete. With your permission, the session will be audio-taped to help the researcher in transcribing and analyzing the data.

CONFIDENTIALITY

The information will be collected from this research will be kept privately. An alias or a pseudo name will be used in the research paper instead of your name; hence, the researcher and his research adviser will only know your identity. Your personal information will be kept safely. It will neither be shared nor given to anyone except to his research adviser.

BENEFITS

There are no direct benefits to you. Your participation will help the researcher in understanding the meanings and concepts you have about smoking. The result of this study will be helpful in crafting smoking cessation programs targeting your population.

As a way of showing appreciation for your time and contribution, you will be provided with a minimum amount to compensate for data used during the storytelling session.

VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION

Your participation is voluntary – it is up to you whether or not you take part in this study. If you decide to contribute, you will be asked to sign a consent form. After signing, you are still free to withdraw at any stage with or without giving a reason. Withdrawing from this study will not affect the relationship you have, if any, with the researcher. If you withdraw from the study before data collection is completed, your data will be returned to you or destroyed.

CONSENT

I have read and I understand the provided information and have had the opportunity to ask questions. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason and without cost. I understand that I will be given a copy of this consent form. I voluntarily agree to take part in this study.

Participant's signature _____ Date _____

Investigator's signature _____ Date _____

Note: Some parts of the form are adopted from Roane State Community College's consent form.

ANNEX C

RESTORYING AND NARRATIVE THEMATIC ANALYSIS

Sample of Restorying Process

Characters	Settings	Problem	Actions	Resolution
Parents, Eduardo, Mosquitoes	Back in the day, Parang	There were a lot of mosquitoes.	Eduardo's parents smoked. Eduardo saw his parents smoked. Ben imitated his parent to smoke.	Mosquito did not bite Eduardo.

The plot

Sample of a Restoried Story

Back in the day, my parents were also smokers. I always saw them smoking before because of our situation in Parang, where there were a lot of mosquitoes. That's why I also imitated what they were doing, because according to them, smoking can shove off mosquitoes. That's why I also smoked so that mosquitoes wouldn't bite me. (Eduardo)

Narrative Thematic Analysis

Theme	Narratives/ Interview Excerpts
Parents and Peer's Influence	
Parent's Influence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It seemed we inherited smoking from our descendants. My father and mother were smokers before. When I saw them smoking, I didn't see any problem. So I thought it was okay to smoke, especially since they took care of us and strived hard to provide for our needs. So by the time my parents caught me smoking, they didn't reprimand or scold me. Instead, they only said 'you take it slowly since you're still studying... if you decide to continue doing this vice just like what we do, it's okay as long as you don't take your studies for granted.' So, it was really okay for them. I didn't experience being scolded by them, never. After that confrontation, there were times that my father left me with two cigarettes in between the leaves of my notebook before I went to school since my allowance was only a peso or one peso and 50 centavos. I just looked for the cigarettes in my notebook every morning. (Anton) (Restoried) • Back in the day, my parents were also smokers. I always saw them smoking before because of our situation in Parang, where there were a lot of mosquitoes. I also imitated what they were doing, because according to them, smoking can shove off mosquitoes. That's why I also smoked so that mosquitoes wouldn't bite me. (Eduardo) (Restoried) <p>On our corn farm before, there were a lot of insects. When we gleaned the weeds and put fertilizers on the young corn, I always smoked to shove off insects, especially those flying insects, the 'langi' that go into our eyes and ears. Those insects were a great disturbance at work. So if we don't have a cigarette, we'd always put on our masks. Otherwise, we couldn't concentrate at work. My father even told me that it was okay to smoke because the cigarette smoke helped the insects to go away. (Eduardo) (Restoried)</p>
Peer's Influence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before, my grandfather had a lot of carabaos. That's why he'd always ask my father, who was in grade 1, to move the carabaos into the pasture early in the morning. There my father would meet his childhood friends, who were older than him, and taught him how to make and smoke a roll-hand cigarette. There were times that my father wouldn't be able to go to school because of that. So that's how my father became a smoker. (Anton) (Restoried) <p>Friends were also influential. Because what you see from your friends, you always follow. (Anton) (Excerpt)</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When I was in high school, I became friends with smokers and alcohol drinkers like Juan [pseudonym] who now lives in the neighboring barangay. They offered me a cigarette by saying ‘you should try this because we’re men and this is our way of life. Your father is also a smoker.’ Every lunch break, after we ate our lunch, we’d go to Neneng’s (pseudonym) sari-sari store to drink and smoke. So when the classes resumed at 1 PM, we had already enough. (Anton) (Restored) • When I was still a teenager, my friends introduced me to cigarette smoking. There were several times that they tried to teach me how to do it but I declined. I was not tempted. Until such time that I tried it myself at home, without their presence, out of curiosity. Eventually, I got addicted to it. I always looked for it and then started to bond with my friends. (Ben) (Restored) • If I’m with my friends, our conversations can go intimate especially when there are cigarettes. Whenever I see a friend lights a cigarette, another friend will then follow and everyone else in the group. Although I try to control it, I’m still tempted to light too because my companions are enjoying it. I have to smoke so that I can keep up with them. I feel like it is very boring if not all of us smoke. (Ben) (Restored) • I always go with my friends when I reached 18 years old. because they [friends] were smokers, I was always curious what it tasted like so they tempted me to try it so I tried it. After some time, I realized that it tasted good. So that’s where it all started. (Dionicio) (Interview extract) • My friends told me “try it, try it!” That’s how it started. (Gibo) (Excerpt)
Means to Manage Negative Feelings and Emotions	
Stress	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I have an older sibling who always depended on my parents’ help. In every harvest, he’d always ask for his share even if he didn’t bother to help. I became problematic and stressed because of that. They [family members] all knew that I was problematic. That’s why I always stayed at the nearest small billiard hall and played there. While I was stroking the ball, I also smoked heavily and drank liquor and I would then go home at 1 AM. When I woke up at 5 AM, I would then visit my carabao, cow, and horse... resume working, and visit the rice field. If I felt that I already finished my work, I would go to the billiard hall again. There was a time when this incident became a repetitive activity, so much so that the hall became my house, where I slept. My mother, who was very compassionate and knew what I was going through, would even bring me food at the billiard hall because I had not been going home. (Anton) (Restored) • There was a time when I was so stressed because of family trouble. I was teenager back then. Because of that, my parents were on the verge of separating. Every time they quarrel at home, I would always visit our farm alone and smoke there intensely to get away from stress and to forget about the problem. Although the relief was just temporary, I

Tiredness	<p>resorted to it because I didn't have someone to share my problem with. I was also shy to talk about it to my friends. (Eduardo) (Restoried)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I smoke when I'm doing farm labor, just like in the rice field. You're exposed to the heat of the sun and the work requires a lot of strength. That's when I crave a smoke. During morning and afternoon breaks and lunchtime when we [fellow farm laborers] can relax, it feels good and reinvigorating every time I inhale the smoke. (Ben) (Restoried) • <i>Hmm</i>, when my back aches [while working on the farm], my hip already hurts. When I stand, I also smoke. And then rest. It's not good to smoke while you're shoveling the rice dikes because it suffocates you. That's why I smoke when it's already rest time. When my body is quite rested, I then pick cigarette and smoke there on the side. (Dionicio) (Excerpt)
Anxiousness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Last month, my fellow laborers and I were contracted by someone to deliver logs from Gensan to a furniture shop here in Bukidnon. Approximately at 3 PM, on our way going back here to Bukidnon, we got into an accident. The truck that we were riding, carrying the logs, lost its breaks. We jumped off the truck and most of us were injured and fractured. I fainted. When gained my consciousness back, I looked for my companions to check if they were okay. I then realized that my left foot hurt as it hit a huge rock after landing on the ground. I was very nervous, looked pale, and I couldn't think properly. Then I smoked cigarettes. It calmed me and redirected back my thoughts. That always happens to me every time I got nervous like at home, whenever I accidentally break a glass and plate, I smoke for me to relax. We were then brought to the nearest hospital to get treated. I was very thankful to God for giving me another chance to live. (Ben) (Restoried) • Manual harvesting of rice requires that you should be fast so that your group can go home early and escape from the scorching heat of the sun. Since we're in hurry, there was a time when my sickle accidentally slightly cut the nail of my little finger. I got so nervous because it was bleeding heavily. I got more nervous when one of my companions said that 'oh my, you looked pale, Caloy!' The health center was too far away from our location. I was then assisted by one of my companions and asked him to give me cigarettes so that I could calm down. I got slightly calmed while puffing my cigarettes. They then told me to go to the health center and have the wound cleaned and dressed. When the midwife saw my wound, she told me, 'oh, your wound is quite large!' So, I got nervous again, all the more when she poured alcohol on my wound; it was really painful. When I got home, the pain was still there it was like there was a beating sensation. So I smoked again to calm myself and for me to forget that I had a wound. I think smoking was the one that really helped me calmed. (Caloy) (Restoried)
Hatred and Irritation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There was a time when I got a broken heart. It was when I discovered that my girlfriend and my close friend had an affair while I and my girlfriend were still in a relationship. Of course, I got hurt. I even thought of beating up my friend because of that. But I couldn't do it. I was so angry and stressed and my thoughts were everywhere. During that time, I would always smoke at home to the extent that I could consume more than 1 pack of cigarettes every day and fill up

<p>Boredom</p>	<p>fully the ashtray. It relieved my stress. Until such time that I got over my stress and overthinking over my ex and friend's affair. (Ben) (Restoried)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Back when I was still in high school, my father was a gambler. That's why the money which could have been used for our daily needs and my schooling was instead betted on cockfighting. You know, I have a lot of siblings who he should support. I really hated him and got easily irritated because of his gambling. That time, I always smoke to relieve my hate to him. Sometimes, I went to my friend's house, smoke, and sleep there for days. My mother even fetched me there. I graduated high school through self-support, like doing farm labor. But I didn't pursue college because of financial problems. (Ben) (Restoried) • Rice farm labor is not always and harvesting only happens every after 3 months. Hence, there were instances when I worked on a poultry farm as coop maintainer. There I fixed the bamboo floor, especially when the bamboos were rotten or fragile. We were individually assigned in each cage. For example, one person was assigned to cages 1 and 2 and another one to cages 3 and 4. So, I didn't have anyone to talk to because we were apart. I was really bored during breaks. I tried to vanish the boredom away by watching the hens laying eggs. But looking at them for a long time could be very boring. To completely get rid of it, I picked up cigarettes in my pocket and lit them. That's why I always bring cigarettes with me because whenever I'm bored, I can have something to puff to brush it off. (Caloy) (Restoried)
<p>Loneliness</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Out of 5 siblings, I'm the middle child. There was favoritism in our family before. That's why after graduating from high school, I was not able to go to college because my parents prioritized my older siblings, who didn't even do good in school. In 1986, I got all the farmland that my parents were maintaining because I became the breadwinner of the family. I had no time with my friends. I only focused my attention on providing for the needs of my family. Vices like smoking and drinking alcohol were my companion before. When I got the chance to build my own house while still supporting my parents, cigarettes and alcohol were still with me. When I moved to a new place, I met a few friends. There were times that I accidentally met them in a sari-sari store. I only bought them cigarettes and alcohol but I didn't stay longer. After taking one shot, I went home. Sometimes, they would tell me 'come over to our place and let's cook chicken' but I always declined. I only focused on my livelihood but cigarette and alcohol were always present. Until such time that I moved here to Sitio Lalawan where I met my wife and build my family. (Anton) (Restoried) • Smoking is my companion because I'm always alone here on the farm. I treat it like a friend. Before when I was a teenager, I had a lot of friends, who taught me how to smoke. We enjoyed each other's company. Now that most of them are married and I'm still single, we seldom see each other. I can always think of them when I smoke here. I feel like I have also companions here even if I'm just alone. (Felimon) (Restoried)

Thought Provoker and Organizer	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A few years ago, I think 2016 or 2015, when we just moved here, I only knew a few people here. That's why I had a hard time looking for someone to ask for jobs. I had also yet to know how to do farm work because I didn't have experience doing one before. It came to a point when my family could barely eat in a day. I was very problematic and I felt ashamed to ask for the help of my wife's uncle again and again, because ever since we moved here, he had been supporting us financially, even giving us rice. When we had only a few foods left, I didn't eat and instead prioritize my kid and wife. during those times, my thoughts were everywhere and so I rummaged all my things, my jeans' pockets, and bags to look for coins to buy cigarettes. After I smoked, I felt relaxed and my thoughts were realigned, and then slept over them and everything that bothered me. And so after two months of staying here, there was a time when I was puffing my cigarettes and got an ingenious idea. I asked myself 'why not I approach people and learn how to do farm work here?' So I tried to approach a lot of new people but I was shy. So what I did before I talked to them was to light cigarettes, and then slowly walked towards them asked them and if they could give me a job. Sometimes, I offered cigarettes to those, I knew, who smoke. So there, we then became friends and they included me in their next schedule of farm labor. (Ben) (Restoried) • It felt lighter when you smoke, especially when you're struggling thinking about something. (Caloy) (Excerpt) <p>One of my farming jobs is rice drying on the solar dryer. When it is dried, we [farm laborers] then put it in the sacks and transfer them to the storage area. There was a time when I couldn't arrange them [the sacks of rice] properly. I was having a hard time doing it. I rested for a while. I also smoked so I can plan well. It was when all the ideas overflowed. And after that, I collected all my ideas, applied them and then successfully piled all the sacks of rice. It weaved my thought. (Caloy) (Restoried)</p> • You can relax your mind when you smoke. Like you can think of things that you need to do next. (Dionicio) (Excerpt) <p>Aside from being a farmworker, I'm also a Habal-habal driver. If I can, I'm the one who fixes my motorcycle if something happens to it. There was this incident wherein I had a hard time fixing my motorcycle's engine in our house. I accidentally dismantled one of its parts and had a hard time putting it back again. I couldn't really fix it to the point that I got angry. I even called my friend over the phone but I couldn't reach him because of a poor signal. So I took a rest for a while and lit one stick of cigarette. I was smoking and watching the dismantled pieces of the engine. After I finished smoking, I suddenly remembered how I did it before. I said, "oh, yes, this is how I should do it." I gathered all the pieces and assembled them again. I think during that time, smoking helped me with my problem. It helped me think well. (Dionicio) (Restoried)</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sometimes when making plans and then while working. It can help when you make plans while puffing. It clears my mind. (Gibo) (Excerpt)
Culture among Friends	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Even more when you have a companion to talk to who is also a smoker. That's the time that you smoked endlessly. (Anton) (Excerpt) For example, when I make rounds on the rice field. I accidentally saw my friends from afar who were visiting their farm as well. Of course, I couldn't avoid not to approach them. I then lit my cigarette and asked them 'do you have cigarettes there?' They said 'yes, I have,' so all of us started smoking. We then talked about what we have noticed on our farm and just anything. I can't go to the rice field without a pack of cigarettes and there were times that my friends had no cigarettes due to no budget so I always shared by saying 'here's a stick, let's smoke.' 1 to 2 hours were too short for that and then 3 sticks were just the minimum number we could consume. In that span of time, the conversation continued. If we can't feel the heat of the sun on our back, we don't go home until such time that one of us will say 'hey, I think it's already lunchtime. I'm starving.'" (Anton) (Restored) • There was even an instance in 2010, when my friends and I, who were still teenagers, got some wise ideas on how to secure some cigarettes. That time, we're heading to the nearby river to catch some fish and bond. The river was our usual place to hang out. While we're on our way going there, we realized that we didn't have some cigarettes and we didn't have money to buy one. We then decided to ask for cigarettes from the sari-sari store and pay them later by the time we had money from farm work. Since I was the only one in the group who was quite close to the sari-sari store owner, I did the honor to ask him. So the owner gave me some. In the river, while we're catching fish, we also always smoked since it was cold. While we're sitting and grilling our catch, we smoked as well. When we're talking about anything, especially nonsense, we intensely smoked with a resounding laugh. It was always nice to talk with my friends while smoking. We can talk about a lot of things. (Caloy) (Excerpt) • I also have friends who always share their cigarettes. If I don't have one, I can always ask from them. Even if the price of cigarettes is already high, they're still the same. They always give. (Caloy) (Excerpt) • When I meet my friends who are also chain-smokers. We'd talk about work, family, and livelihood. While we're talking, we're also smoking. (Eduardo) (Excerpt) • During gatherings, if my friends don't have cigarette, we always share and then smoke together. We sometimes use duhat leaves because cigarettes are pricey. That's the extension of our vices. (Eduardo) (Excerpt) • When we gather with my friends. While we're talking, we also smoke. Even before we start talking, our mouth is already busy puffing cigarettes. We only stop smoking if we're already out of money. We always feel good when we smoke. It makes our conversation fun. (Gibo) (Excerpt)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In our gatherings, I felt like it's very boring if not all of us smoke. Whenever I see a friend lights a cigarette, another friend then follows and everyone else. As I see them enjoying it while talking about things like where to bond next, I'm also enticed to smoke. I have to smoke so that I can keep up with them. (Ben) (Excerpt)
An Integral Part of Life	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It happens by the time I wake up. I drink my coffee and after that, I start using cigarettes. It is delightful when you smoke after drinking coffee. Others even drink coffee while smoking because they make the cigarette as 'pulutan' (snack) for their coffee. According to them, it tastes good. But in my case, I drink coffee first, and then smoke after that. (Anton) (Excerpt) • I always pair my coffee with cigarettes because it's tasty. While you're having your coffee while smoking, you can always think about a lot of things just like you want to turn back the time and then you want to correct all those bad things that you did before. Like If I had taken my life seriously before, I could have finished college. And then your mind is more relaxed when you smoke. Like that. It's like your mind is calm. (Ben) (Excerpt) • When I wake up, drink coffee, and eat breakfast, I then smoke after to remove the disgusting after-taste. (Dionicio) (Excerpt) • I smoke after I drink coffee. (Eduardo) (Excerpt) • After eating breakfast. But from the time I drink coffee up to eating breakfast, 5 sticks are just the minimum that I can consume. The same number of sticks is also minimum to what I can light after breakfast until lunchtime. (Anton) (Excerpt) • What I feel is that, every meal, my body always looks for it. I really want to smoke because my body looks for it. Especially after you drink coffee, I really like to smoke because I felt like I salivate if I can't smoke. (Eduardo) (Excerpt) • It feels nice. It's like your habit, your vice. When I feed the chickens, I smoke. A 10-minute interval between starting and finishing a stick is too long. You made it part of your behavior that you do every now and then. For example, we're seated like this. While you're seating, you feel like there's something missing, and then your cigarettes are on the table, so you get another one, and light it while talking. There will always be a time when you want to smoke, you don't want to end it. When I was still single before, whatever type of work I was in when I got the chance to smoke, I always smoked. While my hand was busy working, my mouth was also puffing cigarettes. In a way, I made it my partner in life. (Anton) (Restoried)

- The moment I wake up, my body always looks for it. It's like, when I wake up, that's the first thing that comes into my mind, saying 'I like to smoke.' Because of addiction, I'm addicted already. I always think of it. (Caloy) (Excerpt)
- It was some time in 2010, I already graduated in high school, when my fellow smoker friends and I decided to go to the nearby river to bond and catch fish. While we're on our way to the river, we realized that we didn't have cigarettes. That time, we didn't have any money to buy one. Since the saris-sari store owner knew me more than the rest of my friends, I took the lead of borrowing some packs of cigarettes on a condition that I would pay him when I got a farm job. So the owner gave me. (Caloy) (Restoried)
- Every now and then. It's continuous. After I finish one stick, I light another one. Like that. But I light another one after an hour. If my feeling likes to smoke, I smoke because I have packs of cigarettes because I have money to buy. I don't ask from others. (Dionicio) (Excerpt)
- Because my feeling always looks for it. Because if I see somebody smoking, I also like to smoke. I feel like I'm attracted to smoke. (Dionicio) (Excerpt)
- What I feel is that, especially after eating, drinking coffee, my body always look for it. It's like I always crave to smoke especially after drinking coffee because I salivate when I can't smoke. I have already made it a habit that during that time, I smoke. (Eduardo) (Excerpt)
- The moment I wake up, I get 2 sticks of cigarettes. Before I cook food and eat my breakfast, I can also consume another 2 sticks. I make cigarette as my companion and pastime here on the farm. (Felimon) (Excerpt)
- I smoke every morning. Sometimes, before coffee and eating. I always smoke. I don't know... I got used to it. I feel so good everytime I smoke. My day wouldn't be complete without it. (Gibo) (Excerpt)
- There was one morning when I woke up after intense smoking the day before, I felt something very irritating in my throat. It was really sore. And then my hair is like being pulled and got a headache that went down to my neck. Then, I smoked again and took medicine. The sore throat and headache were gone. The next day, the same thing happened in the morning. My throat and head hurt. I then smoked for the pain to go away. So every time that happens to me, I always smoke. I feel like cigarettes have become their treatment. (Ben) (Restoried)
- I think because of this repetition, smoking becomes my addiction and can eventually cost me a lot of money especially now that the cigarette is pricey. If I get hospitalized because of this, I cannot afford given our situation. Others even say that it is safer to drink liquor than to smoke cigarettes because a cigarette contains approximately 100 chemicals. That's

why it can be harmful to our bodies and cause addiction. Despite this, I still continue to smoke because my body always craves it. (Ben) (Excerpt)

- I'm also scared because I always look for it. I'm kind of scared but oftentimes I can't resist to smoke. And then sometimes, I feel tired if I can't smoke. That's what I use as my bases that it has bad effects. And If I stop, maybe I become bedridden. I'm scared, but not really, because we cannot do anything if God claims back our lives. [Dionicio] (Excerpt)
- As of now, I still continue smoking because I'm used to it. I got it from my parents. My parents are already 83 years old, and I have not seen them getting sick because of cigarettes. Others would even say that smoking can be bad for our health, but my parents' case is different. So smoking is really okay. (Eduardo) (Excerpt)
- For me, I have a feeling that my smoking habit can have negative effect on my health. If I stop doing it, I think it would also be good, especially now that cigarette is pricey, I can save up money. But something would then be missing. If there's no cigarette, it would be hard for me because I've already gotten used to it. My body looks for it every time. (Felimon) (Excerpt)
- It might be harmful to health but I don't know why I can't stop it. I had tried to stop it before but after 3 days, I go back to smoking again. My mind is always reminded that I should smoke. Maybe they put something to it. (Gibo) (Excerpt)

Asked what will happen to him if he stops smoking

- I don't know. Maybe my lungs will be affected because maybe the nicotine is the only thing that holds it. Because I feel tired if there's no cigarette. (Gibo) (Excerpt)

Asked to cite an example of experience wherein smoking was found detrimental on relationship

- I had a girlfriend who didn't know that I'm a smoker early on our relationship. There was a time when I went to the nearby river to wash my motorcycle. And then later on, I felt cold. There was a sari-sari store owned by Manang Inday so I asked cigarettes and promised her to pay in the future since I didn't have money. That's why after how many days, I think 3 days, Manang Inday and my ex-girlfriend saw each other in the market. From afar, Manang Inday shouted to my ex-girlfriend saying 'Caloy smoked because he said he was cold! He borrowed cigarettes from me!' That's the first time my ex-girlfriend knew that I'm a smoker. That's the cause of our fight. But I always find ways to smoke. (Caloy) (Restoried)

ANNEX D

CERTIFICATE OF PROOFREADING

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that **REYMARK PADLA MALINDA**, author of the research paper titled '**COMMUNICATION AS A SOCIAL PRACTICE: EXPLORING THE MEANING OF SMOKING AMONG FARMWORKERS IN SITIO LALAWAN, MALAYBALAY CITY, BUKIDNON**,' has submitted the manuscript of the said paper to be edited and proofread by me prior to his final submission and publication.

In this connection, the paper is assured to have passed quality check in terms of grammar, mechanics, and organization.

Given this 24th day of September 2022.

For whatever purposes this certification may serve.

Signed,

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